

PATTERNS OF ANEMIA IN GERIATRIC AGE GROUP

By

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BLDE University, Bijapur, Karnataka*

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of

DOCTOR OF MEDICINE

IN

PATHOLOGY

Under the Guidance of

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2013

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

Anemia is a common concern in geriatric age group (more than 60 years of age) and can have significantly more severe complications than anemia in younger adults. Hence our aim is to evaluate the proportion & morphologic patterns of anemia in geriatric age group.

OBJECTIVES:

To study the proportion and morphological patterns of anemia in elderly patients.

METHODS :

A cross-sectional study of 654 cases of patients of geriatric age group (60 years & above) who have attended geriatric clinic, clinical OPDs & IPDs were studied. A detailed history, complete general physical examination and systemic review of the patients undertaken. Detailed laboratory studies of diagnostic tests were done to fix proportion & patterns of anemia.

RESULTS:

Out of 654 cases, 448 were found to be anemic amounting to 68.5 percentage. Proportion of anemia found to be around 2.1/3. Percentage of anemia in males was 67.6% and in females it was 69.8 percentage. All the patterns of anemia were evident. Normocytic anemia being the commonest pattern constituting 78.1% & the next common was microcytic anemia accounted for 11.6% followed by 6.02% of macrocytic anemia & 4.2% of dimorphic anemia.

CONCLUSION:

Confirming the proportion & patterns of anemia is critical to direct the investigation for profiling the etiology since it is well known that the treatment of anemia goes a long way in improving the overall outcome and quality of life.

KEY WORDS: Anemia; elderly; proportion; patterns.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS USED (In alphabetical order)

ACD	Anemia of chronic disease
Fe	Iron
Hb	Hemoglobin
IDA	Iron deficiency anemia
MCH	Mean corpuscular hemoglobin
MCHC	Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration
MCV	Mean corpuscular volume
NCNC	Normocytic normochromic
NCHC	Normocytic Hypochromic
RBC	Red blood cells
RDW	Red cell distribution width
TIBC	Total iron binding capacity
WBC	White blood cell
WHO	World Health organization

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INTRODUCTION

Anemia is a common concern in geriatric age group and can have significantly more severe complications than anemia in younger adults. All the types of anemia are known to occur in this age group & failure to evaluate anemia could lead to delayed diagnosis of potentially treatable conditions¹.

The decline of hemoglobin and concomitant increased anemia with age is not necessarily, a result of “normal aging”, because anemia is a sign and not a diagnosis. An evaluation is almost always warranted to identify the underlining cause, thus early detection of anemia is an important topic in an older person & should prompt appropriate clinical attention².

Anemia in the elderly can occur in both acute and chronic settings. Multiple pathophysiologic abnormalities in a single elderly patient with anemia are well known. It is essential therefore that the treating physician is aware of the coexistence of anemia in elderly, although the presenting manifestation may be for a different reason. Untreated anemia in geriatric population is associated with greater risk of death, co-morbidities, and impaired functional status. It becomes therefore pertinent to look for severity of anemia, type of anemia, possible etiologies and appropriate correction³.

Studies indicate that the prevalence of anemia increases with advancing age and under age 75 years, anemia is more common in females, but over age 75 years it is more common in males.³ Using World Health Organization criteria for anemia, the prevalence found to range from 8 to 44 percent, with the highest prevalence in men 85 years and older.¹ As reported in the Indian cross-sectional studies prevalence varies between 6% and 30% among males and between 10% and 20% among females. Population based studies in Great Britain have reported prevalence ranges from 5% to 25%.^{2,3}

Despite the high prevalence of anemia in the elderly and the increasing size of the geriatric population, only few studies have examined the effects of anemia on elderly patients². There are no data on Indian population as such is available, hence our aim is to document proportion and patterns of anemia as a part of health profile in geriatric age group attending a tertiary care hospital.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study the Proportion and Morphological patterns of anemia in geriatric patients attending a tertiary care hospital.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Using World Health Organization criteria, anemia is defined as hemoglobin less than 12 g per dL in female and less than 13 g per dL in male. It is a common clinical problem at all ages, but this is especially true among the geriatric age group (more than or equal to 60 years)². According to epidemiologic data, its prevalence among adults increases sharply after this age group. As a rise in the aging population has been predicted and the prevalence of anemia is expected to rise sharply in the future.³

In elderly persons, the etiology of anemia differs sufficiently from younger adults to warrant considering anemia in elderly persons as a distinct entity⁴. The most common causes of anemia in elderly are chronic disease and iron deficiency. Vitamin B12 deficiency, folate deficiency, myelodysplastic syndrome are among other causes.^{5,6}

Experienced clinicians recognize the non specific nature of many illnesses like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and left ventricular dysfunction may produce symptoms similar to that of anemia. Orthopnea, dyspnea at rest and extensive edema are produced only if anemia is severe enough to produce circulatory congestion^{6,7}. Careful studies of anemia have indicated that such symptoms may not be associated with anemia until hemoglobin levels lower than 7-8 gm/dl. However there is a paucity of data documenting the prevalence of symptomatology of anemia in elderly patients⁸.

The manifestations such as fatigue, dyspnea on exertion, palpitation, anorexia, faintness, lack of concentration, drowsiness and angina and severity of anemia vary considerably among individuals.⁹ It is also associated with mortality and poorer health-related quality of life, regardless of the underlined cause of the low hemoglobin¹⁰.

It is easy to over look anemia in the elderly since symptoms of anemia may be attributed to the aging process itself.¹¹ Anemia should not be accepted as an inevitable consequence of aging as it may be an important sign that often points to a serious and possibly treatable medical condition^{12,13}.

NHANES-III of WHO study revealed prevalence of anemia 11% of men and 10.2% of women aged 65years and older. According to an analysis of the Third National Health And Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III), 34% of anemia in older adults was due to folate, B12, or iron deficiency alone or in combination. Twenty percent had anemia of chronic disease (ACD), 12% were associated with renal insufficiency and the remaining 34% were unexplained.¹

Chul won choi et al in his study of anemia in elderly observed that out of 1254 patients 171 were anemic. Out of them 144(11.4%) were women and 27(2.1%) were men. A significant difference in prevalence of anemia was found among the age 60-69 years, 70-79years and 80 and above years. The most common pattern of anemia in his study was found to be normocytic anemia amounting to 93.5% and 3.5% of them were microcytic, and 3% of them were macrocytic anemias.²

Ramachandra SS et al has showed in his study that 17.7% of the subjects were anemic based on the cut-offs prescribed by the WHO.³

Celestin Roux et al reported particularly high prevalences for men in all age groups, ranging from 42.8% in men aged between 70 and 74 years to 59.5% in men 85 years⁴.

Salive et al examined the association between anemia in the elderly and morbidity and Hospitalization⁵.

Hee-seon Kim et al in his study observed that out of 562 subjects, 70 subjects (25 men and 45 women) were anemic. The prevalence rate of anemia was 12.3%. The prevalence of anemia was the lowest among age group of 60-69 years followed by age group of 70-79 and the highest among the age group over 80 years. The most common pattern of anemia in his study was found to be normocytic anemia amounting to 90.2% and 0.9% and 8.9% were microcytic and macrocytic anemias respectively.⁶

Jack M. Guralnik et al revealed that overall, 11.0% of men and 10.2% of women 65 years and older and living in the community are anemic according to WHO criteria.⁷

Stefano Muzzarelli has shown that anemia proved to be an independent predictor of death and major clinical adverse events among elderly patients with stable symptomatic coronary artery disease.⁸

Artz AS et al showed that 14% to 50% of anemic elderly had no obvious underlying cause.⁹

Lesourd 2004 studies showing that chronic under nutrition in older persons is associated with a relative down regulated immune response and low lymphocyte counts, which were the two main correlates of unexplained anaemia.¹⁰

Nissenson et al study revealed that prevalence of anemia in general elderly population was 7.5% for males & 20% for females ¹¹.

Elis et al have shown that most common anemia in elderly is normocytic normochromic type.¹²

Gerbrand J.Izaks et al have shown that a low hemoglobin concentration at age signifies disease¹⁵.

Milman N et al has shown that about 5.8% of the total anemia population had myelodysplastic syndrome. And 17.2 % of the patients had unexplained anemia¹⁶.

Carmel et al has shown that the highest rates of anemia occur in hospitalized Populations¹⁷.

Kikuchi et al studied the relation between anemia and mortality in the elderly¹⁹.

Amit Bhasin et al study shows that most common pattern of anemia was normocytic & commonest cause of anemia was anemia of chronic diseases⁴⁴.

Anemia

Anemia, is not a diagnosis in itself, but is an objective sign for presence of disease. Anemia is defined as a condition in which the concentration of hemoglobin in peripheral blood is below the level that is normal for the level for that age and sex of an individual¹³. The normal limit of hemoglobin concentration varies among definitions established by different organizations. World health organization criteria for anemia are hemoglobin less than 12 g/dl in women and less than 13 g/dl in men. This definition is the most frequently used¹⁴.

EVALUATION OF ANEMIA IN ELDERLY

Anemia in the elderly is evaluated in a manner similar to that in younger adults, including an assessment for signs of gastrointestinal blood loss, hemolysis, nutritional deficiencies, malignancy, chronic infection (such as subacute endocarditis), renal or hepatic disease, and other chronic disease¹⁵. In patients without evidence of an underlying disease, the initial laboratory evaluation should include a complete blood count, red blood cell indices, a reticulocyte count and peripheral blood smear^{16,17}.

Anemia algorithms used for evaluation of younger adults are based on the mean corpuscular volume. Such algorithms may be less helpful in the elderly because the classic changes in erythrocyte size do not often accompany anemia in this age group¹⁸. In most elderly patients with anemia, red cell indices disclose normocytic, normochromic

anemia. It also should be remembered that the cause of anemia is not always found. A bone marrow examination is rarely necessary in initial evaluation of anemia in older patients^{19,20}.

The vast majority of uncomplicated anemia can be diagnosed without a bone marrow examination. However the procedure should be performed when the anemia is accompanied by abnormalities in WBC or platelets or when marrow infiltration is suspected. The examination is no more dangerous or painful in older people than in younger people^{21,22}.

ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF ANEMIA IN ELDERLY.

Table 1- Common causes of Anemia in the Elderly ²³

Cause of Anemia	Percentage of Cases (%)
Anemia of chronic disease (ACD)	30 to 45
Iron deficiency	15 to 30
Post hemorrhagic	5 to 10
Vitamin B12 and folate deficiency	5 to 10
Chronic leukemia or lymphoma	5
Myelodysplastic syndrome	5
No identifiable cause	15 to 25

NORMOCYTIC ANEMIAS

ANEMIA OF CHRONIC DISEASE

Anemia of chronic disease, also called anemia of chronic disorders, is the most common form of anemia in the elderly^{25,26}. Numerous diseases are associated with anemia of chronic disease, but in many cases an underlying disease is not identified. The hematologic abnormality in anemia of chronic disease is an impaired ability to use the iron stored in the reticuloendothelial system. Erythrocytes are usually normochromic and normocytic, but about one third of patients with anemia of chronic disease have microcytosis^{27,28}.

Anemia of renal disease

In renal insufficiency, a normochromic anemia develops which is very similar to Anemia of chronic disease (ACD). In this condition there is a deficiency of erythropoietin production, and there is evidence that the administration of erythropoietin, when the anemia is severe, can partially improve the condition^{29,30}.

Anemia of endocrine disorders

Endocrine disorders that commonly produce anemia are hypothyroidism, hypopituitarism, and adrenal insufficiency. In all three diseases the anemia is normocytic and normochromic but may be macrocytic³¹.

Anemia of liver disease

In liver diseases, a normocytic or macrocytic anemia develops. There are many causes of anemia in liver disease, including bleeding, iron deficiency, folate deficiency, hypersplenism, and sideroblastic anemia^{31,32}. In liver disease, however, serum iron is increased and there is an increase in transferrin saturation. Serum ferritin is also increased and often reflects total body iron overload³³.

Anemia of collagen vascular diseases

Anemia of chronic disease appears in collagen vascular diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, polyarteritis, dermatomyositis, systemic lupus erythematosus, and temporal arteritis (including polymyalgia rheumatica)^{31,34}.

“Unexplained anemia” of elderly people

A mild, normocytic normochromic anemia with a hemoglobin concentration usually between 11 and 12 g/dL has been reported in people over the age of 70. This anemia cannot be accounted for any underlying disease or deficiency, and the bone marrow does not contain ringed sideroblasts. This unexplained anemia is said to account for over 30 percent of the anemias in this age group^{29,35}.

Anemia of cancer in elderly

The incidence and prevalence of cancers increases with age. Anemia is present in more than 60% of cancer patients and the risk of anemia is higher with more advanced stages of cancer. The most common mechanisms of anemia in cancer patients are chronic inflammation and myelotoxic treatment such as chemotherapy and radiation therapy^{36,37}.

MICROCYTIC ANEMIA

Iron deficiency anemia

Iron deficiency anemia, the second most common cause of anemia in the elderly, usually results from chronic gastrointestinal blood loss caused by nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug induced gastritis, ulcer, colon cancer, diverticulum or angiodysplasia³⁸. Chronic blood loss from genitourinary tract cancer, chronic hemoptysis and bleeding disorders may result in iron deficiency but are much less common causes. Older persons may become iron deficient because of inadequate intake or inadequate absorption of iron³⁹.

Other Causes of Microcytic Anemia -:

Anemias caused by abnormal hemoglobin (e.g. sickle cell anemia) are usually not first diagnosed in old age. Thalassemia minor, since it is asymptomatic, may first be found in old age. The anemia of chronic disease may be microcytic, but it is more commonly normocytic. Sideroblastic anemia may be microcytic, normocytic, or even macrocytic⁴⁰.

MACROCYTIC ANEMIA

Macrocytic anemia is described as an anemia in which the MCV is greater than 100 fl. MCV increases slightly with increasing age but usually not enough to produce significant macrocytosis. Relatively few disorders routinely result in macrocytic anemia. The two common disorders that produce macrocytosis are megaloblastic anemias due to either vitamin B12 or folate deficiency^{26,40}.

MYELOYDYSPLASTIC SYNDROME

Myelodysplastic syndrome is a relatively uncommon cause of anemia, but is a more common cause in the elderly than in younger patients⁴¹. The syndrome is characterized by a defect in the development of one of the marrow cell lines, limiting the release of functioning cells. Anemia results when the red cell lines are affected. Myelodysplastic syndrome should be a diagnostic consideration when white cell or platelet abnormalities accompany the anemia. The diagnosis of this syndrome is usually made by bone marrow aspiration & biopsy^{42,43}.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Source of Data

Patients of geriatric age group [60yrs and above]⁶ who have attended geriatric clinic & clinical OPD's & IPD's in BLDE University Shri B.M.Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bijapur, Karnataka, India during the period between November 2010 to April 2012.

Method of Collection of Data

A cross-sectional study of 654 patients satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, managed by Departments of pathology, BLDE University Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Bijapur Karnataka were studied. Detailed history of included patients were elicited. A complete general physical examination and systemic review of the patients were undertaken.

The following investigations have been carried out for all the patients:

Hemoglobin (g/dl)

Total leukocyte count & differential leukocyte count

Platelet count.

Erythrocyte sedimentation rate [ESR],

Packed cell volume [PCV],

RBCs indices -: MCV, MCHC, MCH & RDW.

Peripheral smear study

Reticulocyte count.(if indicated)

Bone marrow aspiration study was carried out wherever necessary.

Additional investigations as indicated for detection of underlying cause [upper GI endoscopy and colonoscopy, tissue biopsy, imaging-CT/MRI] were carried out wherever necessary.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

All the geriatric patients of either sex who have attended geriatric clinic, clinical OPD's & admitted to IPD's were included.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients with a history of recent blood transfusion

Patients who have undergone major surgical procedure in the past 3 months.

Patients who were on haematinics , Vitamin B12 or folic acid.

Study Design

Observational study (Cross Sectional Study)

Sample Size:

With prevalence rate of Anemia among elderly is 33% (Average prevalence of 6-30% among male & 10-20% among female)², and considering 99% level of confidence and 20% allowable error,

Using statistical formula

$$n = \frac{(2.56)^2 p (1-p)}{L^2}$$

p = Prevalance rate of anemia among elderly people =33%

L = Allowable error =20%

The calculated sample size was 333.

But 654 prospective cases were studied in particular duration.

As per **WHO criteria**, anemia is defined as hemoglobin count < 13g/dl in males and < 12 g/dl in females¹.

Patterns of anemia are classified based on RBC indices & further correlated by peripheral smear. Microcytic anemia was defined as MCV below 80 fl, normocytic as MCV between 80 and 100 fl and macrocytic anemia by an MCV above 100 fl. Dimorphic anemia are suspected when RDW is more than its normal range(11-15%) & then correlated by peripheral smear.⁴⁴

Table – 2. Severity²⁴ of anemia graded as mild, moderate & severe

Severity	World Health Organization
Grade 1 (Mild)	10-11.9 gm / dl
Grade 2 (Moderate)	7.1-9.9 gm / dl
Grade 3 (Severe)	<7 gm / dl

RESULTS

PART 1: BASE LINE DATA

Table: 3 – Distribution of study subjects according to sex

Gender	Number of subjects	Percentage
Male	392	59.9
Female	262	40.1
Total	654	100

Figure: 1- Pie chart showing distribution of study subjects according to sex

Table: 4- Distribution of study subjects according to their age

Age Group	Number	Percentage
60 - 69 yrs	385	58.9
71 - 79 yrs	201	30.7
>80 yrs	68	10.4
Total	654	100

Figure: 2- Bar diagram showing distribution of study subjects according to their age

Table: 5- Distribution of study subjects according to age and sex

Age in years	Total	Sex	
		Male	Female
60-69	385	226	159
70-79	201	125	76
>80	68	41	27
Total	654	392	262

PART 2: RESULTS ON PROPORTION OF ANEMIA AMONG STUDY SUBJECTS

In this study, the Proportion of anemia found was 2.1/3 i.e. 68.5% in BLDEU Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & RC, Bijapur, Karnataka. Percentage of anemia in males was 67.6% and in females it was 69.8 percentages.

Table: 6- Percentage of anemia in study subjects according to sex

Sex	Anemia		Total	Percentage
	Yes	No		
Males	265	127	392	67.6
Females	183	79	262	69.8
Total	448	206	654	68.5

Figure: 3- Bar diagram showing percentage of anemia in study subjects according to sex

Table: 7- Percentage of anemia in study subjects according to age

Age in years	Anemia		Total	Percentage
	Yes	No		
60-69	257	128	385	66.7
70-79	137	64	201	68.1
>80	54	14	68	79.4
Total	448	206	654	68.5

Figure 4 – Bar diagram showing Percentage of anemia in study subjects according to age

Table 8 – Distribution of anemic study subjects according to severity.

Sex	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Male (265)	180	60	25 (9.3%)
Female (180)	113	62	8 (4.4%)
Total (448)	293	122	33
Percentages	65.4	27.3	7.3

Lowest hemoglobin found was 1.8g/dl in males & 3.9g/dl in females.

Figure 5 – Bar diagram showing distribution of anemic study subjects according to severity.

PART 3: RESULTS ON PATTERNS OF ANEMIA

For the study of patterns of anemia we took all 448 anemic patients among the study subjects.

Table: 9- Distribution of the anemic subjects according to patterns of anemia

Patterns of anemia	Frequency	Percentage
Normocytic normochromic	313	69.8
Normocytic hypochromic	37	8.25
Microcytic hypochromic	52	11.6
Macrocytic	27	6.02
Dimorphic	19	4.24
Total	448	100

Figure: 6 – Bar diagram showing distribution of anemic subjects according to patterns of anemia

Figure: 7 – Pie chart showing distribution of the study subjects according to patterns of anemia

NORMOCYTIC ANEMIA

Table: 10 -Distribution of Normocytic anemia according to sex

Gender	Number	Percentage
Males	207	59.4
Females	143	40.6
Total	350	100

350 patients of the total 448 anemic patients had underlying normocytic anemia. Out of the 350 patients, 207 were males and 143 were females.

MICROCYTIC ANEMIA

Table: 11- Distribution of patients of microcytic anemia according to sex

Gender	Number	Percentage
Males	31	59.6
Females	21	40.4
Total	52	100

52 patients of the total 448 patients had underlying microcytic anemia. Out of the 52 Patients, 31 were males and 21 were females.

MACROCYTIC

Table: 12- Distribution of macrocytic anemia according to sex

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	15	55.5
Female	12	44.5
Total	27	100

27 patients of the total of 448 anemic patients had underlying macrocytic anemia. Out of the 27 patients, 15 were males and 12 were females.

DIMORPHIC ANEMIA

Table: 13- Distribution of dimorphic anemia according to sex

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	12	63.2
Female	07	36.8
Total	19	100

19 patients of the total of 448 anemic patients had underlying dimorphic anemia. Out of the 19 patients, 12 were males and 07 were females.

Fig.- 8. Normocytic normochromic anemia - Leishman's stain (100x)

Fig – 9. Microcytic Hypochromic anemia – Leishman's stain (100x)

Fig – 10. Macrocytic anemia – Leishman's stain (100x)

Fig – 11. Dimorphic anemia – Leishman's stain (100x)

DISCUSSION

Aging is associated with increased incidence and prevalence of anemia, that is associated with a number of adverse health outcomes. These include functional dependence, increased risk of therapeutic complications, falls, dementia and death. In approximately 30% of cases, anemia in older individuals is due to either relative or absolute erythropoietin deficiency. Absolute erythropoietin deficiency may be primary or secondary to declining renal function. Relative erythropoietin deficiency is due to an age-related pro-inflammatory status that reduces the sensitivity of erythropoietic precursors to erythropoietin^{2,8}.

Despite this condition of erythropoietin deficiency, the management of anemia of aging with erythropoiesis stimulating factors (ESF) is controversial, unless the anemia is due to renal insufficiency¹⁶. The main concern related to this treatment arises from eight studies of ESFs in cancer, suggesting that ESFs may reduce patient survival, in addition to increasing the risk of deep vein thrombosis^{17,18}.

Anemia in elderly is a frequent, underappreciated and potentially morbid condition. However, public health improvement for the anemic elderly involves a complex set of scientific, clinical and societal issues³². Anemia is associated with symptoms ranging from weakness and fatigue, palpitations, depression and in severe cases can lead to

congestive cardiac failure. Age related disability and loss in physical function are growing public health priorities. Loss in physical function threatens the independence and quality of life of older adults and has substantial social and economic effects³³.

Although it was previously believed that decline in hemoglobin level might be a normal consequence of aging, evidence has accumulated that anemia does reflect poor health and increased vulnerability to adverse outcome in older persons. The decline of hemoglobin and concomitant increased anemia with age is not necessarily a result of "normal aging" so the detection of anemia in an older person should prompt appropriate clinical attention^{19,20}.

In our study percentage of anemia calculated was 68.5% while according to **WHO report (2000)**¹⁴, prevalence of anemia in older individuals is about 50% in developed countries and 12% in developing countries.

In Present study, percentage of anemia in male was 67.6% & in females was 69.8%. While **NHANES-III of WHO**⁴⁵ study revealed prevalence of anemia in 11% of men and 10.2% of women aged 65 years and older. However ours study was a hospital based as compared to this study which was population based.

In our study percentage of anemia in males (67.6%) was less as compared to females (69.8%) in contrast to **Guralink J.M et al**²⁰ whose study showed that 11.0% of men and 10.2% of women of 60 years and above are anemic.

In present study percentage of anemia was lowest among age group of 60-69 years (66.7%) followed by 70-79 years (68.1%) age group and the highest among the age group over 80 years (79.4%). Most common pattern in present study was found to be Normocytic anemia accounting for 78.1%. **Hee-seon Kim et al**⁶ study correlates closely with present study.

Our study revealed that proportion of anemia increases with age which is confirmed by **Celestin Roux et al**⁴ study.

Present study shows that most common anemia in elderly is normocytic normochromic type (69.8%). In order of type of anemia **Elis et al**¹² study corroborates with present study.

In present study percentage of anemia was 68.5%, of which Normocytic being the commonest constituting 78.1% followed by microcytic 11.6%, macrocytic 6.02 & dimorphic 4.2%. **Ania et al**¹ diagnosed anemia in 36% of males, being normocytic in 83%, microcytic in 14% , and macrocytic in 3%, as compared to 44% of women ,which

was microcytic in 16%, normocytic in 80%, and macrocytic in 4% of cases. Hence our study closely tallies with this study, depicting normocytic anemia being the most common in both males and females.

SUMMARY

Patients of both the sexes, above the age of 60 years were included between the period of November 2010 to April 2012. Percentage of anemia in geriatric age group calculated was 68.5%, accounting to proportion around 2.1/3 of study subjects. In females it was more (69.8%) than males (67.6%). Percentage of anemia increased with age, i.e. highest in > 80 years age group (79.4%) followed by 70-79 years age group (68.1%) & lowest in 60-69 years age group (66.7%).

All the types of anemia were evident. Normocytic being the commonest, constituting 78.1% followed by microcytic 11.6%, macrocytic 6.02 & dimorphic 4.2% in either sex & in different age groups of study subject.

Majority of Anemia was found to be mild (65.4%) followed by moderate (27.3%) & severe (7.3%) . Severe anemia was found to be more in males (9.3%) as compare to females (4.4%) & severity of anemia increased with the increasing age.

Fatigue was the most common symptom encountered in the anemic population.

CONCLUSION

Anemia is a significant common association in the elderly and its proportion in the present study was found to be 2.1/3, which is high may be because study was done in tertiary care hospital. Proportion of anemia found to be slightly increased in females as compared to males. Most common patterns of anemia found was normocytic followed by microcytic, macrocytic & dimorphic in either sex & different age groups. Majority of the anemia was mild in either sex & severity increased with increasing age groups.

Confirming the patterns of anemia is critical to direct the investigation for profiling the etiology since it is well known that the treatment of anemia goes a long way in improving the overall outcome and quality of life.

Hence, it is necessary to evaluate the anemia status in all elderly patients as a part of health profile in geriatric age group.

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ANNEXURE I

PROFORMA FOR STUDY OF ANEMIA

Demographic Details:

Name:

Age :

Sex: M/F

OPD / IPD no.:

Present history:

Past history:

Including history of any major surgery

History of blood transfusion

History of drug intake & haematinics

Any other

Personal history:

Habits: Smoking/Alcohol/Any other

Physical Examination :

Pulse rate

BP

RR

Pallor / Icterus / LN /Pedal Edema / Bony Tenderness

Fundoscopy

Others

Per Abdomen Examination:

Respiratory System Examination:

Cardiovascular System Examination:

Central Nervous System Examination:

Investigations:

HB :

TC :

DC :

ESR :

PLATELET COUNT:

MCH :

MCV :

MCHC

PCV :

BONE MARROW STUDIES (As Indicated)

Additional investigations if necessary for detection of underlying cause.

UPPER G.I ENDOSCOPY AND COLONOSCOPY

S.ELECTROPHORESIS

TISSUE BIOPSY

IMAGING

CT/MRI

DIAGNOSIS

ANNEXURE II

PROCEDURE :- Leishman's Stain

REAGENTS:-

Leishman powder - 0.15gm

Methyl Alcohol (acetone free) – 100ml.

Leishman powder :- Equal quantities of polychromed Methylene Blue (1 %) and Eosin B (0.1%)

PROCEDURE :-

- 1) Air dried film was flooded with leishman's stain for 2 minutes.
- 2) Double the volume of buffer water was added for 10 minutes.
- 3) The stain was washed off with distilled water until it acquired a pinkish tinge.
- 4) After drying, the back of the slide was wiped clean.
- 5) The slide was mounted with D.P.X

ANNEXURE III

HEMOGLOBIN	MALE	13.0-17.2 gm/dl
	FEMALE	12.0 – 15.1 gm/dl
HEMATOCRIT	MALE	40.7- 50.3%
	FEMALE	36.1- 44.3%
MCV		80-97.6 fl
MCH		27.6-33.7 pg
MCHC		32.7 – 33.5 gm/dl
RETICULOCYTE COUNT		0.5 – 1.5%

MASTER CHART

S.No	Name	IP/OP	Age	Sex	Smoker/ Alcohol	Fatigue	H/O blood loss	Clinical diagnosis	Hb (g/dl)	PCV (%)	Platelet (in lakhs)	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (gm/dl)	TC /mm ³	ESR	Anemia	Type of anemia
1	Vishwanath	10054	60	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10.6	30.3	1.93	93.5	33	35	23,200	40	Y	NCNC
2	Laxmibai	9983	75	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	9.8	26.7	2.13	82.9	30	36.7	4,500	80	Y	NCNC
3	Guru	9912	85	M	Y	Y	N	Altered sensorium	9.8	31.2	1.25	93.1	29	31.4	14,800	85	Y	NCNC
4	Ningappa	10077	84	M	Y	Y	N	Fever with chills	10.7	29.5	0.8	102	37	36.3	7,700	40	Y	Macrocytic
5	Gurupadaya	6249	75	M	N	N	N	Fever	13.9	38.2	1.6	91	35	34.1	11,200	25	N	N
6	Savitri	6285	60	F	N	N	N	Inf.wall MI	12	35.4	2.13	84.1	37	33.4	6,800	55	N	N
7	Laxman	5874	80	M	Y	Y	N	Pneumonia	8.6	25.3	2.65	79.5	36	30.9	8,400	100	Y	NCNC
8	Veerappa	6300	80	M	Y	Y	N	Eczema	10.3	30.9	1.67	92.4	38	32.4	9,200	25	Y	NCNC
9	Chanabasappa	5783	72	M	N	N	N	Fever, cough	14.9	41.6	2.33	81	35	36.2	12,600	50	N	N
10	Shivanna	5841	70	M	Y	N	N	Convulsion	13.5	39.1	4.12	72.1	30	30.6	6,800	20	N	N
11	Channamma	5856	65	F	N	Y	N	Fracture	5.3	17.1	1.67	67.9	28	32.1	7,600	90	Y	MCHC
12	Sushilabai	67665	64	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.8	34.4	1.3	82.3	33	38.4	8,100	45	Y	NCNC
13	Y.B.Hanjagi	68440	62	M	Y	N	N	Bronchitis	15.1	45.6	2.16	85.6	32	36.7	7,800	10	N	N
14	Paramma	5871	60	F	N	N	N	Cough	14.6	43.1	1.96	83.6	34	36.2	5,400	20	N	N
15	Hanamawwa	5876	70	F	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	12.5	34.6	2.68	92.8	36	38.2	7,400	25	N	N
16	Tarabai	5820	60	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.8	33.6	1.99	78.6	33	36.8	4,200	60	Y	NCNC
17	Sangappa	5849	60	M	Y	N	N	Gastritis	15.4	46.1	1.62	91	36	38.7	5,600	10	N	N
18	Chinnawwa	5063	85	F	N	N	N	Bronchitis	12.4	36.1	5.21	83.6	32	36.4	6,800	50	N	N
19	Subhadrabai	59135	65	F	N	N	N	Cough	13	40.1	4.86	79.6	33	35.4	5,100	50	N	N
20	Chandrakant	54771	62	M	N	N	N	Swelling of neck	13	39.2	0.9	77.6	30	36.1	4,000	40	N	N
21	Mandakini	59066	60	F	N	Y	N	DM	11.6	32.8	3.12	79.8	30	37.6	9,100	60	Y	NCNC

22	Sangappa	59504	65	M	Y	N	N	TB	12.7	37	2.61	80.9	32	38.6	4,600	80	Y	NCNC
23	Abdul	5091	60	M	N	N	N	Swelling of neck	13.1	41.2	2.65	86.2	34	36.9	5,800	70	N	N
24	Sytunabi	5105	65	F	N	N	N	Cough	11.9	47.2	4.16	90.2	36	38.2	6,200	5	N	NCNC
25	Lasgivappa	5109	85	M	Y	N	N	Dermatitis	13.3	37.1	1.96	82.1	31	38.2	14,600	55	N	N
26	Shivalingappa	5097	65	M	N	N	N	Pneumonia	13	40.1	2.58	86.9	32	39.6	12,000	5	N	N
27	RP Chavan	7139	63	M	N	N	N	DM	16.7	46.2	2.18	88.2	32	38.9	6,100	5	N	N
28	Basagouda	6205	73	M	Y	Y	N	Urinary retention	11.1	33.6	4.22	69.1	29	32.6	8,900	55	Y	MCHC
29	Lalsab	6150	61	M	N	Y	N	HTN	9.1	28.2	1.98	85.6	32	36.9	15,800	90	Y	NCNC
30	Padwage	5717	60	M	Y	Y	N	Haemorrhoid	6.6	62.2	1.65	79.6	32	36.5	5,200	90	Y	NCNC
31	Dasarat	5427	70	M	N	N	N	Liver trauma	12.6	36.9	3.21	83.5	32	38	6,800	5	Y	NCNC
32	Satamma	5994	70	F	N	Y	N	Cerebral malaria	11	34.1	2.14	78.6	31	36.4	20,500	20	Y	NCNC
33	Sonabai	3566	65	F	N	Y	N	Burn	11.3	33.9	2.68	85.9	33	38.6	8,200	40	Y	NCNC
34	Ratnabai	75160	65	F	N	Y	N	Prolapse	11.7	35.4	1.57	88.1	34	39.7	4,100	35	Y	NCNC
35	Madia	6653	75	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	8.3	25.6	3.14	79.6	32	36.8	4,300	20	Y	NCNC
36	Guruliamma	6531	70	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	12.7	36.1	4.37	83.1	34	38.1	8,600	80	N	N
37	Shivappa	5775	60	M	Y	N	N	Abscess	13.1	39.2	5.17	82.6	36	38.9	14,800	40	N	N
38	Sharanamma	67363	80	F	N	N	N	Joint pain	12.1	36.4	4.67	90.6	34	35.9	4,600	45	N	N
39	Annanya	5785	70	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	8.4	25.6	2.65	78.6	28	36.1	9,400	120	Y	NCNC
40	Mingappa	5750	80	M	Y	N	N	UTI	13	40.6	5.23	88.6	31	36.4	5,900	40	N	N
41	Padmavati	3921	65	F	N	Y	N	Gluteal abscess	8.1	26.1	2.66	66.2	24	30.2	6,800	60	Y	MCHC
42	Halakatteppa	5798	71	M	N	Y	N	Lower limb#	10.4	32.1	3.14	85.6	32	36.9	6,500	115	Y	NCNC
43	Surnappa	5822	60	M	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	13	39.6	2.52	88.9	36	38.5	12,600	35	N	N
44	Neelamma	67334	72	F	N	Y	N	Fever & cough	10.1	32.3	3.23	79.3	31	36.2	4,000	115	Y	NCNC
45	Basappa	4662	85	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10.6	31.2	2.62	81.3	33	39.6	5,800	60	Y	NCNC
46	Bhermiya	5770	65	M	Y	N	N	Chest pain	14.2	43.2	4.63	89.6	33	36.4	9,200	25	N	N
47	Sonawwa	5739	68	F	N	N	N	IHD, DM	13.2	39.6	4.65	92.1	32	39.2	8,400	50	N	N
48	Ansuyaa	5527	67	F	N	Y	N	Rheumatoid arthritis	7.8	22.3	2.67	79.2	30	36.2	8,200	130	Y	NCNC
49	Lakkawwa	5490	71	F	N	N	N	Abscess	12.6	37	2.99	88.2	33	35.4	5,600	50	N	N
50	Shantamma	5541	60	F	N	N	N	Fever	11.1	36.2	2.12	82.1	31	39.1	3,100	20	N	NCNC
51	Anand	10777	68	M	N	Y	N	Unconsciousness	9.8	28.1	2.66	79.2	30	36.5	4,600	40	Y	NCNC

52	Neelakanth	10701	78	M	Y	Y	N	Chest pain	10.5	31.6	1.6	78.1	32	35.2	9,400	60	Y	NCNC
53	MB ARIF	95903	63	M	N	N	N	Fever	14.4	42.2	2.92	86.1	32	36.4	7,600	5	N	N
54	Jayashree	8105	70	F	N	N	N	Cough	11.3	34.6	1.3	78.2	30	34.6	9,200	45	Y	NCNC
55	Boramma	8172	60	F	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	12.6	37.2	1.69	84.2	33	36.8	5,400	10	N	N
56	Laxman	8183	67	M	Y	N	N	Pain abdomen	12.7	38.1	2.13	82.6	33	38.6	6,800	90	Y	NCNC
57	Kusma	8180	69	M	N	Y	N	Vomiting	11.7	33.6	2.76	79.6	33	38.6	7,400	20	Y	NCNC
58	Parvati	122070	70	F	N	N	N	Urticaria	13.2	40.1	1.62	82	31	33.7	6,900	45	N	N
59	Tukaram	10514	75	M	N	Y	N	Pain in Lt thigh	11.8	36	4.32	78.6	29	36.2	14,800	40	Y	NCNC
60	Gangamma	35984	65	F	N	N	N	Bullous pemphigoid	12.8	37.4	2.63	82.6	33	36.2	5,600	30	N	N
61	Siddawwa	10483	60	F	N	N	N	Abdoman distension	14.5	43.6	3.2	90.2	34	36.3	12,800	5	N	N
62	Basappa	10246	70	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	12.3	36.6	4.26	82.2	32	36.5	5,400	95	Y	NCNC
63	S.M.Badiger	10272	72	M	N	N	N	Abscess	15.2	45.6	2.64	83.6	33	38.4	6,800	10	N	N
64	Sankerappa	9286	65	M	Y	N	N	Tonsillitis	12	36.2	1.35	79.2	33	36.2	6,900	10	Y	NCNC
65	P K Jadhav	107328	62	M	N	N	N	Cough	14.2	43.2	2.58	83.6	31	36.4	9,900	5	N	N
66	Neelkam	107936	60	M	Y	N	N	Inguinal swelling	14.1	44.6	4.2	88.6	34	39.6	13,800	10	N	N
67	Anusya	107963	69	F	N	Y	N	RA	11.9	33.6	2.69	79.6	33	38.2	5,500	90	Y	NCNC
68	Mallappa	107546	66	M	N	N	N	Myalgia	14.1	43.2	1.46	92.1	34	38.1	19,600	5	N	N
69	Bhimangouda	9265	60	M	Y	N	N	Acute GE	12.6	44.1	3.15	86.2	32	37.2	12,100	5	N	NCNC
70	Neelawwa	9230	76	F	N	N	N	HTN	11.6	37.6	2.76	88.2	33	36.1	9,600	40	N	NCNC
71	Basappa	9155	63	M	N	N	N	Dermatitis	14.3	44.6	1.85	78.2	31	35.9	8,600	70	N	N
72	Shivappa	106390	71	M	Y	N	N	Cough	14.9	44.2	2.58	92.3	34	39.2	16,400	40	N	N
73	Sidawwa	106983	62	F	N	N	N	Fever	10.9	31.6	0.9	69.1	30	34.6	8,900	20	Y	MCHC
74	Rumabai	115935	65	F	N	Y	N	Bleeding PV	13.1	40.2	2.63	79.6	301	36.1	5,500	10	N	N
75	Laxmibai	115703	71	F	N	N	N	Prolapse	14.6	43	1.32	83.9	31	36.9	9,200	25	N	N
76	Tarappa	10069	80	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.9	35.2	1.91	78.6	31	35.6	10,600	60	Y	NCNC
77	Shantabai	10040	70	F	N	N	N	Bronchitis	12.2	36.9	3.63	82.6	32	36.5	9,600	50	N	N
78	Shantabai	117175	60	F	N	N	N	Breathlessness	14	43.1	4.16	88.2	33	38.6	11,400	80	N	N
79	Vishwanath	10057	60	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10.6	31.3	1.96	77.6	29	36.2	8,400	80	Y	NCNC
80	Laxmibai	9983	70	F	Y	N	N	Fever	9.8	28.6	2.35	80.9	32	39.2	13,400	80	Y	NCNC

81	Gurupadappa	9912	83	M	N	Y	N	Altered sensorium	9.8	29.6	2.66	79.6	30	36.3	8,600	85	Y	NCNC
82	A S Kori	96670	63	M	Y	N	N	Cough	14	43.2	1.49	88	33	35.6	14,600	5	N	N
83	Bourawwa	8258	60	F	N	N	N	Fever	13.4	38	4.25	85.4	33	36.9	3,000	10	N	N
84	Simderela	96775	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	12.3	37.4	1.69	78.6	32	36.2	5,800	30	N	N
85	Davalsab	8282	62	M	Y	Y	N	Vomiting	11.5	34.2	3.69	88.2	32	36.4	9,800	35	Y	NCNC
86	Rindawwa	8273	62	F	N	N	N	Hernia	12.2	36.8	1.36	79.2	30	36.5	8,800	60	N	N
87	Bangalemma	97790	75	F	N	N	N	Prolapse	12.3	38.2	4.32	85.2	33	35.9	5,200	30	N	N
88	Konakul	97021	65	F	N	N	N	Cough	11.9	38.4	1.66	78.6	33	36.9	6,600	60	N	NCNC
89	Yamanappa	8392	70	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	10.4	31.2	1.68	80.6	32	37.4	6,900	115	Y	NCNC
90	S.M.Srishail	95055	65	M	Y	N	N	Swelling	18.7	51.3	3.46	92.1	33	37.5	21,300	5	N	N
91	Mallappa	98050	70	M	N	N	N	Fever	12.6	38	2.55	76.9	31	36.2	5,700	60	Y	NCNC
92	Tarabai	98194	70	F	N	N	N	Fever	12	36.8	2.88	92.1	34	38.4	9,100	45	N	N
93	Rukumaddin	8384	65	M	Y	N	N	Vomiting	11.4	33.2	4.16	78.6	30	36.5	12,600	55	Y	NCNC
94	Srinivas	8417	92	M	N	Y	N	Ca Lung	13	40.1	1.86	86.1	30	36.5	6,000	40	N	N
95	Bimabai	8658	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	12	37.5	2.54	83.9	29	35.2	14,800	60	N	N
96	Shrishail	100742	60	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	11.3	35.1	1.88	69.6	27	32.1	18,100	105	Y	MCHC
97	R K Dhakani	91297	67	M	N	Y	N	Inguinal swelling	12	37.2	1.85	83.4	32	38.2	4,600	20	Y	NCNC
98	Mohamadulla	8650	60	M	Y	N	N	# neck of femur	14.8	43.6	2.85	78.6	32	36.8	5,300	40	N	N
99	Amateppa	139706	60	M	N	Y	N	Cough	10.3	30	4.72	80.6	28	34.3	14,700	90	Y	NCNC
100	Mallikarjun	11981	70	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10.5	33.2	2.89	65.6	21	31.6	7,800	65	Y	MCHC
101	Pulabai	133835	85	F	N	Y	N	Lipoma	10.9	32.3	4.88	96.4	33	33.7	15,900	95	Y	NCNC
102	Mallamma	11705	70	F	N	Y	N	Fever	8.9	25.8	0.6	88.7	31	34.5	7,300	85	Y	NCNC
103	Rajasab	11655	70	M	Y	Y	N	AR +MR	7.7	25.4	1.84	67	20	30.3	6,100	25	Y	MCHC
104	Hiremath	137363	78	M	N	Y	N	Swelling lower limb	10.9	32	3.78	87	30	34.1	10,900	55	Y	NCNC
105	Shivappa	11656	85	M	Y	Y	N	DM	10.5	31.4	2.7	85.3	29	33.4	25,900	100	Y	NCNC
106	Shreya	7266	70	M	Y	Y	N	Psoriatic arthritis	8.2	23.9	4.43	88.2	30	34.3	7,400	85	Y	NCNC
107	Sharanbai	8210	64	F	N	Y	N	Swelling over Rt arm	10	27.4	2.99	84	31	36.5	13,100	55	Y	NCNC
108	Banapp	8301	61	M	N	Y	N	Fever	13	38.9	2.32	86.2	30	36.2	9,700	10	N	N
109	Goumawwa	8395	65	F	N	N	N	Breathlessness	14	44	1.39	82	32	34.3	16,200	10	N	N

110	Sonubai	8153	62	F	N	Y	N	Acute GE	10.4	30.3	1.5	91.3	31	34.3	8,900	60	Y	NCNC
111	Irappa	7890	60	M	Y	Y	N	Anemia	8.7	29.7	2.41	74.4	22	29.3	21,900	105	Y	NCHC
112	Pundalik	8006	82	M	N	Y	N	Vomiting	10.3	30.7	2.09	84.6	28	33.6	6,400	55	Y	NCNC
113	Basavantappa	8032	65	M	N	Y	N	BPH	10.5	32.2	1.52	76.7	28	32.6	11,400	40	Y	NCNC
114	Haifbi	8034	70	F	N	N	N	Breathlessness	10.5	32	1.9	75.7	25	32.8	5,800	50	Y	NCNC
115	Sangangouda	8047	60	M	Y	Y	N	TB	10.9	35.5	1081	93.5	29	30.7	9,200	35	Y	NCNC
116	Laxmibai	7817	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	8	23.6	3.7	94	32	33.9	15,900	60	Y	NCNC
117	Abdul	28882	75	F	N	Y	N	# Femur	10.2	29.3	3.1	82.8	29	34.8	15,700	25	Y	NCNC
118	Sonabai	8079	68	F	N	N	N	Fever	8.4	23.8	1.4	92.2	33	35.3	4,500	80	Y	NCNC
119	Laxmibai	2091	60	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	9.8	28.8	2.88	83.7	29	34	9,500	45	Y	NCNC
120	Nuhudenia	10119	60	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	6.2	15.4	1.82	69.7	28	40.3	11,100	85	Y	MCHC
121	Ningappa	17252	65	M	Y	N	N	Cough	12	38	2.03	80	25	31	10,900	50	Y	NCNC
122	M S Biradar	200816	75	M	N	Y	N	Loose stool	12	37	1.66	85	28	32	7,400	25	Y	NCNC
123	Somaning	16842	60	M	Y	N	N	BPH	12.6	37.2	2.1	84	28	33.9	12,900	10	Y	NCNC
124	Gurappa	17321	80	M	N	Y	N	Fever	10.2	30	3.32	88	29	33	8,500	80	Y	NCNC
125	Girimallappa	17349	64	M	N	N	N	UTI	13	39	1.5	79	25	32	10,700	5	N	N
126	Shantabai	17285	80	F	N	N	N	Stroke	9	27	2.09	93	30	33	15,800	30	Y	NCNC
127	Bhimappa	17318	65	M	N	Y	N	Fever	7.8	23.9	1.67	77.6	25	32.6	18,500	50	Y	NCNC
128	Mahadevappa	17872	65	M	Y	N	N	Urinary retention	13.1	40	2.49	88	28	32	9,400	10	N	N
129	Bhimabai	205268	62	F	N	N	N	Fever with chills	13	36	2.79	92	33	35	7,200	50	N	N
130	Jinappa	17428	65	M	Y	Y	N	Hematuria	8.2	26.6	3.47	64.3	20	33	6,500	70	Y	MCHC
131	Shivaji	17894	60	F	N	N	N	Fever	13	38.2	2.5	99	35	36	6,600	10	N	N
132	Tulaja	17883	60	M	Y	N	N	Hematemesis	10.6	31.8	1.93	80	29	36.5	20,100	10	Y	NCNC
133	Anisuya	17870	69	F	N	N	N	Fever	12.9	39.1	2.85	76	25	33	9,800	70	N	N
134	Shivappa	17865	75	M	N	Y	N	TB	9.3	28	3.54	83	27	32	10,900	80	Y	NCNC
135	Revensidappa	17836	75	M	Y	Y	N	DM	11.4	33.6	3.24	92.6	31	33.9	17,700	60	Y	NCNC
136	Lokabai	10090	75	F	N	Y	N	Loose stool	10	28.2	1.5	78.8	28	35.5	14,400	45	Y	NCNC
137	Fakeersab	9227	60	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10.3	33.3	1.72	80.4	25	30.9	16,400	55	Y	NCHC
138	B.R.Bayal	110959	82	M	N	N	N	Fever	10.3	32	2.56	89.4	29	32.2	12,100	60	Y	NCNC
139	Neelabai	10260	60	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10	30.6	3.03	81.4	27	32.7	6,600	45	Y	NCNC
140	Jayalal	10274	68	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	10.6	34.4	2.98	70.5	22	30.8	5,800	85	Y	NCHC

141	Kamalabai	10442	76	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	10.5	28.6	1.99	82.9	30	36.7	7,400	60	Y	NCNC
142	Shrishailappa	10429	60	M	Y	Y	N	Gluteal abscess	4.5	14.5	4.15	63.9	20	31	8,600	100	Y	MCHC
143	Parvati	10396	80	F	N	Y	N	Cough	10.2	31.8	2.28	91.9	30	32.1	19,600	55	Y	NCNC
144	Mallamma	10300	60	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	10.9	32.6	2.73	78.6	26	33.4	8,900	30	Y	NCNC
145	Gangamma	10603	70	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.3	33	2.15	89.2	28	31.2	10,700	35	Y	NCNC
146	Kashibai	10196	88	F	N	Y	N	Prolapse	9.8	28.9	1.97	83	28	33.9	5,600	60	Y	NCNC
147	Chandamma	10618	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.3	31.7	1.79	91.1	30	32.5	8,900	50	Y	NCNC
148	Kallolibai	11701	75	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	5.1	17.1	7.48	55.9	17	29.8	10,700	40	Y	MCHC
149	Parvatamma	11749	50	F	N	Y	N	Altered sensorium	10.6	31.5	2.22	82.5	28	33.7	6,800	95	Y	NCNC
150	Rangubai	11783	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever with chills	3	13.8	6.1	84	26	32.4	13,100	110	Y	NCNC
151	Mallamma	138750	80	F	N	Y	N	Fever	9.8	28.7	2.62	100	34	34.1	6,000	80	Y	Macrocytic
152	Yallamma	11887	60	F	N	Y	N	Inf.wall MI	9.2	28.1	3.28	89.8	29	32.7	6,800	40	Y	NCNC
153	Chandrabarga	138696	70	F	N	Y	N	Pneumonia	10	29.9	2.1	91.2	31	33.4	5,500	80	Y	NCNC
154	Ningawaa	9204	60	F	N	Y	N	Eczema	9	23	3.7	90.2	32	35.2	7,900	100	Y	NCNC
155	Bhagirathi	9771	80	F	N	N	N	Fever, cough	10.9	30.7	1.8	103	35	33.9	13,400	35	Y	Macrocytic
156	Mahadevi	7375	76	F	N	Y	N	Convulsion	10	28	1.6	102	35	36	29,000	25	Y	Macrocytic
157	Mahadev	9567	60	M	Y	N	N	Fracture	9.8	28.2	0.65	93.7	33	34.8	6,700	40	Y	NCNC
158	Mally	9305	70	M	N	Y	N	Fever	8.7	26	2.38	76.7	26	33.5	6,900	80	Y	NCHC
159	Bheema	9463	60	M	N	Y	N	Bronchitis	10.9	30.3	2.36	70.8	26	36	12,800	75	Y	Dimorphic
160	Kashibai	8526	80	F	N	Y	N	Cough	3.6	10.9	1	100.9	33	33.9	4,400	100	Y	Dimorphic
161	Shivappa	99535	92	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	4	11	0.9	120	36	43	3,400	105	Y	Macrocytic
162	Bhimappa	9463	65	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	9.1	25.9	2.69	78.7	28	35.1	23,700	110	Y	NCNC
163	Tarabai	8602	80	F	N	Y	N	Gastritis	10.5	32.1	1.74	94	32	34	7,000	30	Y	NCNC
164	Ningamma	8575	65	F	N	Y	N	Bronchitis	8.8	30.3	2.27	91	25	28	7,300	95	Y	NCNC
165	Mehabuba	8623	70	F	N	N	N	Cough	10.7	30.8	2.65	85	26	32.5	10,300	70	Y	NCHC
166	Laxmibai	7264	70	F	N	Y	N	Swelling of neck	10.8	34	4.12	85	27	31.8	15,000	25	Y	NCNC
167	Shivaturappa	8319	77	M	N	Y	N	DM	10.6	31.2	1.55	87.4	30	34	14,100	30	Y	NCNC
168	Bahujanda	7962	60	M	Y	Y	N	TB	6.4	23	3.12	68	17	26.8	7,000	100	Y	MCHC
169	Shivalingappa	3859	64	M	Y	Y	N	Swelling of neck	10.2	31.4	4.7	95	31	32.5	9,100	35	Y	NCNC
170	Shantabai	89912	75	F	N	Y	N	Cough	7.6	26.3	4	64	19	28.9	14,900	90	Y	MCHC

171	Bhayambi	2996	70	F	N	N	N	Dermatitis	9.1	27.5	2.01	88	29	33	6,900	55	Y	NCNC
172	Annapuram	2609	60	F	N	Y	N	Pneumonia	4.7	15.8	0.7	80.3	26	29.7	8,000	115	Y	Dimorphic
173	Basalingappa	2545	62	M	Y	Y	N	DM	7.2	22	3.8	89.8	29	32.7	13,100	65	Y	NCNC
174	Shivakundabi	2840	60	F	N	Y	N	Urinary retention	10.1	31.2	1.63	94.5	31	32.4	9,400	30	Y	NCNC
175	Siddappa	2594	70	M	Y	Y	N	HTN	8.1	25.4	3.19	87.3	28	31.9	12,000	80	Y	NCNC
176	Noora	2571	60	M	Y	N	N	Haemorrhoid	9	30.1	1.87	72.4	22	29.9	7,400	35	Y	NCHC
177	Vitoba	193320	67	M	Y	N	N	Liver trauma	14.2	43.4	3.25	86.1	28	32.7	7,900	5	N	N
178	Sudakar	192745	77	M	N	N	N	Cerebral malaria	14.9	42.8	1.88	93	32	34	10,000	15	N	N
179	Nabibsab	15657	60	M	N	Y	N	Burn	11.4	33.8	7.98	90	30	33.7	13,100	20	Y	NCNC
180	Sahebgouda	16737	66	M	N	Y	N	Prolapse	9.8	32.7	4.46	67	20	30	16,500	35	Y	MCHC
181	Balwantaya	14503	60	M	N	Y	N	Chest pain	12	36.2	2.7	94.3	31	33.1	6,100	80	Y	NCNC
182	Bhimappa	16714	65	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	12.2	34.5	2.4	91	32	35.4	14,100	5	Y	NCNC
183	Rudragouda	16670	70	M	N	Y	N	Abscess	10.9	37.6	3.41	117	40	34	9,000	35	Y	Macrocytic
184	Guramma	193100	63	M	N	N	N	Joint pain	14.7	44.3	3.13	91.3	30	33.2	7,300	5	N	N
185	Gangadhar	16731	65	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	12.2	37.6	3.02	90.3	30	32	6,100	30	Y	NCNC
186	Sidappa	16725	62	M	N	N	N	UTI	13.4	37.5	2.5	76	25	33.6	19,500	70	N	N
187	Shankarayya	16718	68	M	N	Y	N	Gluteal abscess	10.7	32.1	1.2	87	29	33.5	4,500	20	Y	NCNC
188	Baranagouda	16712	65	M	Y	N	N	Lower limb#	13.5	40	2	86	28	33.2	12,300	40	N	N
189	Gurubasappa	16693	80	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	12.6	38.2	1.72	87.2	27	31	7,700	20	Y	NCNC
190	Bhimarayya	16665	82	M	Y	Y	N	Fever & cough	12.6	36.6	1.5	83.6	29	34.6	6,300	50	Y	NCNC
191	Shivaraj	16681	63	M	N	Y	N	Fever	11.6	36.1	2.3	77.9	24	32.9	11,300	100	Y	NCNC
192	Ayanna	170913	60	M	N	Y	N	Chest pain	11.8	36.5	2.3	108	35	32.3	16,700	95	Y	Macrocytic
193	Gaurabai	17072	65	F	N	Y	N	IHD, DM	11	33.6	3.02	80	26	32.7	7,700	60	Y	NCNC
194	Parvati	197242	67	F	N	N	N	Rheumatoid arthritis	12.1	37.5	3.6	90	29	32.4	8,200	75	N	N
195	Dundamma	197153	70	F	N	Y	N	Abscess	12.7	39.2	4.26	93.2	33	36.5	4,900	10	N	N
196	Anakka	17060	60	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.3	36.3	0.8	78.3	24	30	9,900	25	Y	NCNC
197	Mainya	196847	70	M	N	Y	N	Unconsciousness	11.9	36	2.54	89.3	30	33	7,400	30	Y	NCNC
198	Paramawwa	17006	70	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	8.9	28	1.73	84	27	31.5	4,800	80	Y	NCNC
199	Ramappa	17002	68	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	12.3	37	2.77	100	34	34.5	7,700	5	Y	Macrocytic
200	Dodangouda	17070	75	M	N	N	N	Cough	14.3	43.5	1.65	85	29	32.6	5,800	10	N	N

201	Hanamanth	196683	62	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	13.3	40	2.56	92	30	34.2	6,200	5	N	N
202	Nuchi	196656	71	M	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	13.6	41.5	3.58	85	32	35.6	8,800	15	N	N
203	Basalingappa	17062	68	F	N	Y	N	Vomiting	11.2	34.2	2.22	86.2	29	35.8	12,100	40	Y	NCNC
204	Kashibai	17084	70	F	N	Y	N	Urticaria	9.5	28.9	3.69	82.9	30	32.6	5,100	55	Y	NCNC
205	Janginamath	207655	70	F	N	Y	N	Pain in Lt thigh	10.8	30.4	2.84	76.4	27	35.5	8,500	40	Y	NCNC
206	Maleridda	207707	66	M	Y	N	N	Bullous pemphigoid	14.3	39.5	3.25	80.8	29	36.2	8,700	20	N	N
207	Gurawwa	16534	60	F	N	Y	N	Abdoman distension	11.9	33.2	2.82	79	28	35.8	6,000	35	Y	NCNC
208	Saraswati	17992	70	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	11.2	34	2.42	73.9	24	32.9	7,700	20	Y	NCHC
209	Sidappa	17999	65	M	N	N	N	Abscess	14.8	41.1	2.05	98.6	36	36	9,700	20	N	N
210	Shamra	18011	65	M	N	Y	N	Tonsillitis	11.3	33.8	1.89	79.8	33	34.8	8,500	40	Y	NCNC
211	Shantabai	18030	62	F	N	Y	N	Cough	12.6	39.1	3.11	85.7	28	32.2	7,900	10	N	N
212	Shantappa	18040	70	M	Y	Y	N	Inguinal swelling	10.1	29.3	4.25	73.3	25	34.2	6,700	40	Y	NCNC
213	Jaiban	15965	75	M	N	Y	N	RA	9	25.5	1.5	90.4	32	35.3	9,600	40	Y	NCNC
214	Shiva	184567	70	M	N	N	N	Myalgia	13.2	38	2.63	81	28	34.7	14,500	60	N	N
215	Appasab	15940	78	M	Y	Y	N	Acute GE	9.8	28	3.06	86	30	35.2	8,900	50	Y	NCNC
216	Ramappa	15489	60	M	N	Y	N	HTN	12	38	1.64	79.8	25	31.3	6,700	20	Y	NCNC
217	Abdulla	15905	60	M	Y	Y	N	Dermatitis	10.2	30.2	1.76	84.6	28	33.8	12,900	65	Y	NCNC
218	Rukmani	184724	60	F	N	N	N	Cough	12.7	37.4	2.95	87	29	32.6	5,800	35	N	N
219	Malappa	2E+06	80	M	Y	N	N	Fever	12.7	38.8	6.25	91.6	30	33.2	6,000	20	Y	NCNC
220	Guru	184413	79	M	N	Y	N	Bleeding PV	13.7	40.4	0.9	85.6	29	33.6	15,700	45	N	N
221	Ramanlingappa	184410	71	M	N	N	N	Prolapse	14.2	40.1	2.66	85.6	31	35.4	6,200	30	N	N
222	Lalsab	15884	60	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	10.3	30.5	2.36	85.7	29	33.2	5,900	110	Y	NCNC
223	Sidlingappa	15968	60	M	N	N	N	Bronchitis	14.1	41.4	0.9	88.8	30	34.1	14,100	5	N	N
224	Prema	15887	65	F	N	N	N	Breathlessness	12.7	37.6	1.99	82	28	33.8	7,400	45	N	N
225	Rukamma	15943	75	M	Y	N	N	Pain abdomen	13.2	40.1	3.06	91	30	32.9	19,100	10	N	N
226	Sidappa	4990	60	M	N	N	N	Fever	13.4	39.5	1.79	87.2	30	34	6,900	20	N	N
227	Durga	4200	72	M	N	Y	N	Altered sensorium	5.6	18.7	8.02	61.1	18	29.3	8,200	120	Y	MCHC
228	V.G.Apasangi	50030	78	M	N	Y	N	Cough	11.1	33	1.56	89.7	30	33.6	6,000	35	Y	NCNC
229	Mallappa	4247	60	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	11.7	35.2	2.02	76.5	28	30.2	9,700	40	Y	NCNC

230	Lakshman	15998	68	M	N	Y	N	Fever	13.2	40.2	2.25	93.3	31	32.8	5,800	5	N	N
231	B.D.Mulla	4262	60	M	N	Y	N	Vomiting	12.1	36.2	2.22	83.3	28	33.3	9,900	25	Y	NCNC
232	S.S.Pattar	159882	61	M	Y	N	N	Hernia	14	43.7	3.82	80.3	26	32	10,800	5	N	N
233	Basappa	2125	66	M	N	N	N	Prolapse	12.1	38.1	1.5	84.3	27	31.5	4,600	35	Y	NCNC
234	Shivappa	4267	72	M	Y	N	N	Cough	13.8	40.3	2.41	83.3	28	33.7	8,800	40	N	N
235	Iramma	4270	68	M	Y	N	N	Breathlessness	17.1	50.4	1.76	86.9	30	33.9	16,100	20	N	N
236	Basamma	4653	65	F	N	Y	N	Swelling	11.1	33.2	1.5	93.8	31	33	12,700	30	Y	NCNC
237	Sharanappa	4600	72	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	8.7	27.6	2.6	89.3	28	31.5	7,800	60	Y	NCNC
238	Tarabai	54756	62	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11	34.9	3.03	86.2	26	34	6,400	35	Y	NCNC
239	Neelamma	4610	75	F	N	Y	N	Vomiting	8.3	25	1.79	84.2	28	33.2	5,500	90	Y	NCNC
240	Rudrappa	4603	70	M	Y	N	N	Ca Lung	13.2	44.1	1.85	94.4	28	29.9	7,400	10	N	N
241	Sidappa	4901	79	M	N	Y	N	Fever	11.9	32.6	2.92	91.3	31	34	9,600	50	Y	NCNC
242	Basamma	4585	60	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.9	35.7	2.83	74.7	23	31	7,100	60	Y	NCHC
243	Chandram	3852	65	M	N	Y	N	Inguinal swelling	10.2	30.3	3.47	85.3	27	31.3	8,800	45	Y	NCNC
244	Gangabai	4552	65	F	N	N	N	# neck of femur	11.8	36.1	2.11	108	36	33.8	10,700	65	Y	Macrocytic
245	Basamma	54821	70	F	N	Y	N	Cough	13.8	40.2	2.5	89	29	32.9	9,000	15	N	N
246	Subhdra	54818	80	F	N	N	N	Fever	13.7	41.6	2.69	83.2	27	32.9	7,000	5	N	N
247	Sheetappa	4639	90	M	N	Y	N	Lipoma	15.7	45.6	1.95	86	30	34.4	10,000	20	N	N
248	Mallamma	4290	64	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	11.6	34.2	2.85	93.8	31	33.6	3,600	55	Y	NCNC
249	Dundawwa	50320	75	F	N	Y	N	AR +MR	11.2	34.4	2.59	106	32	32.6	7,000	65	Y	Macrocytic
250	Gurusidappa	18285	76	M	N	Y	N	Swelling lower limb	11.5	38.3	2.05	71.1	21	30	12,400	25	Y	MCHC
251	Siddu	18295	60	F	N	Y	N	DM	11.5	32.7	1.78	84.5	30	35.2	9,800	40	Y	NCNC
252	Tanu	18122	60	F	N	Y	N	Psoriatic arthritis	12.4	36.2	2.09	83.7	28	33.6	6,800	25	N	N
253	Jinappa	17428	65	M	Y	Y	N	Swelling over Rt arm	8.3	27.1	2.25	69.3	21	30.6	8,300	80	Y	MCHC
254	Durgabai	61014	90	F	N	Y	N	Fever	13.1	40.4	1.91	85.1	28	32.4	3,100	60	N	N
255	Baburao	18272	72	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	7.2	22.7	1.99	84.4	28	33.5	18,200	20	Y	NCNC
256	Chamma	18289	70	F	N	Y	N	Acute GE	11	34	3.06	85	27	32.3	5,700	50	Y	NCNC
257	Channamma	18283	65	F	N	Y	N	Anemia	10.9	33.4	2.36	90.3	30	32.6	5,700	55	Y	NCNC
258	Mahadevappa	18284	65	M	Y	N	N	Vomiting	14	44.3	3.58	94.1	30	31.6	7,200	30	N	N

259	Renukabi	18290	65	F	N	Y	N	BPH	11.6	35.9	2.88	95.5	31	32.3	8,600	90	Y	NCNC
260	Biligi	18298	65	M	N	N	N	Breathlessness	13.2	37.7	1.3	81.9	29	35	10,700	5	N	N
261	Kashibai	18235	65	F	N	Y	N	TB	8.9	27.9	0.7	80.4	26	31.9	9,400	5	Y	NCNC
262	Bhimanaya	17424	65	M	Y	N	N	Fever	12.7	37.9	2.3	94.3	32	34.5	4,700	20	Y	NCNC
263	Yalappa	16989	68	M	N	Y	N	# Femur	5.1	17.6	0.53	72.5	23	29	5,200	20	Y	MCHC
264	Shanappa	200890	75	M	Y	N	N	Fever	12.8	37.4	2.34	86.5	30	34.2	8,200	35	Y	NCNC
265	Sidagond	201734	60	M	N	Y	N	Weakness	8.1	28.3	1.68	70.9	20	28.6	8,300	20	Y	Dimorphic
266	Basawwa	17429	60	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	9.5	30.6	3.39	81.6	25	31	18,500	30	Y	NCNC
267	Sadasur	16930	70	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	9.9	30.7	3.33	93.3	30	32.2	8,800	50	Y	NCNC
268	Shanta	17392	85	F	N	Y	N	Loose stool	11	33.8	2.31	84.2	28	32.5	11,900	10	Y	NCNC
269	Shaila	17436	70	F	N	Y	N	BPH	11.8	37.3	2.71	79.5	25	31.6	14,000	30	Y	NCNC
270	Shanu	18263	68	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.9	37.5	2.38	72	23	31.7	5,500	60	Y	MCHC
271	Shrishail	210278	72	M	Y	Y	N	UTI	11.2	32.4	1.75	85	29	34.6	3,000	90	Y	NCNC
272	Yenkappa	18254	76	M	N	Y	N	Stroke	14.1	42.8	2.79	88.6	29	32.9	7,600	15	N	N
273	Donnul	18221	68	M	Y	N	N	Fever	15.2	42.5	1.74	99.5	36	35.8	6,600	5	N	N
274	Ramagond	18211	60	M	N	N	N	Urinary retention	13	40	1.8	86	28	32.5	11,900	30	N	N
275	Adaveppa	210182	76	M	N	Y	N	Fever with chills	9.5	27.9	1.87	82.5	28	34.1	5,300	80	Y	NCNC
276	Putlabai	209360	70	F	N	Y	N	Hematuria	11	31.7	3.31	71.7	25	34.7	8,300	5	Y	MCHC
277	Danayya	17565	78	M	N	Y	N	Fever	12.4	36.2	3.96	81.2	28	34.3	16,400	100	Y	NCNC
278	RazIbai	18127	64	F	N	Y	N	Hematemesis	9.6	30.3	5.96	77.5	25	31.7	20,200	45	Y	NCHC
279	Basamma	209371	70	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.9	35.6	3.85	81.5	27	33.4	20,200	40	Y	NCNC
280	Shankaryya	209496	65	M	N	N	N	TB	14.4	42.9	2.7	82.3	28	33.6	6,900	10	N	N
281	Gangawwa	18237	75	F	N	Y	N	DM	8.4	26.8	3.93	78.6	25	31.3	9,300	30	Y	NCNC
282	Laxman	18050	65	M	N	Y	N	Loose stool	11.6	37.3	1.57	90.5	28	31.1	6,600	25	Y	NCNC
283	M.H.Allur	208543	80	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10.5	33	4.4	68	22	31.8	9,500	20	Y	MCHC
284	Tippamma	15294	66	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10.1	30	2.57	83.5	29	33.6	8,800	100	Y	NCNC
285	Kasturibai	209117	60	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10.3	33.2	5.87	73.6	23	31	7,300	20	Y	NCHC
286	Husanappa	18135	75	M	Y	N	N	Weakness	13.8	40.6	3.89	78.2	27	34	18,000	15	N	N
287	Lingappa	15104	75	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	10.1	32.4	5.2	86.9	27	31.2	13,700	55	Y	NCNC
288	Biradar	18125	62	M	Y	Y	N	Gluteal abscess	10.7	33.7	4.96	80.6	26	31.8	11,800	100	Y	NCNC
289	Kheeru	18038	65	M	N	Y	N	Cough	10	28.5	1.7	75	26	35.1	4,800	40	Y	NCNC

290	Sherayya	17958	65	M	N	Y	N	Chest pain	10.3	28.8	1.28	78.5	28	35.8	7,400	20	Y	NCNC
291	Chinnamma	18096	75	F	N	Y	N	Fever	14	40.2	2.46	80.1	28	34.8	14,300	15	N	N
292	Madawallapa	18165	78	M	N	N	N	Prolapse	13.8	42.1	2.56	83.4	27	32.8	9,300	30	N	N
293	Hanamanth	188961	60	M	N	N	N	TB	13.6	38.4	1.4	99.2	35	35.4	9,100	70	N	N
294	Shiva	16298	64	M	Y	N	N	Fever	15.2	46.4	1.2	87.9	27	32.9	17,200	20	N	N
295	Dharansingh	16194	70	M	N	Y	N	# Femur	10.5	31.4	4.79	79.4	27	33.4	11,600	55	Y	NCNC
296	Ananna	16255	60	M	Y	N	N	Fever	13.2	42.4	2.85	93.2	30	32.6	4,600	5	N	N
297	Sangappa	188758	80	M	N	Y	N	Weakness	12.3	37.3	1.92	84.6	28	33	14,200	10	Y	NCNC
298	Pulabai	188758	60	F	N	N	N	Chest pain	11.7	36.2	2.28	85.2	28	32.3	7,100	25	Y	NCNC
299	Madevi	188968	64	F	N	N	N	Cough	12.8	38	4.68	88.2	30	33.7	7,500	50	N	N
300	Yallowwa	188457	65	F	N	N	N	Loose stool	13	38.7	2.69	83.4	28	33.6	5,100	5	N	N
301	Ningappa	16240	83	M	Y	N	N	BPH	10.2	33.7	2.59	76.7	29	35.5	13,900	45	Y	NCNC
302	Anamma	16251	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.2	32.1	2.34	82.7	29	34.9	6,900	60	Y	NCNC
303	Bangaramma	16273	60	F	N	N	N	UTI	12.8	38.4	3.29	104	35	33.6	11,600	65	Y	Macrocytic
304	Dahayya	17563	76	M	N	Y	N	Stroke	11.3	34.5	1.74	83.3	27	32.8	7,300	50	Y	NCNC
305	Hanamant	17549	65	M	N	N	N	Fever	10	31.2	2.01	73.6	24	32.1	6,400	20	Y	NCHC
306	Maktunsab	17554	70	M	Y	N	N	Urinary retention	13	42.3	1.5	85.5	29	32.6	4,800	5	N	N
307	Jadhav	17320	70	M	Y	Y	N	Fever with chills	11.8	35.9	5.63	90.7	30	32.9	23,000	25	Y	NCNC
308	Chandramma	17493	60	F	N	N	N	Hematuria	12.9	39.4	3.16	84.7	28	32.7	12,600	20	N	N
309	Nagappa	202273	65	M	Y	N	N	Fever	12.8	37	3.56	97.1	34	34.6	8,000	40	Y	NCNC
310	Mahanteppa	198345	68	M	Y	Y	N	Hematemesis	9.8	29.9	2	82.8	27	32.8	7,100	60	Y	NCNC
311	B.C.yalawar	202149	70	M	N	Y	N	Fever	13.6	42.2	1.65	86.1	28	32.2	10,000	5	N	N
312	Shimanth	202092	60	M	Y	N	N	TB	15.6	46.5	1.95	91.2	31	33.5	8,100	10	N	N
313	Jehera	202196	64	M	N	N	N	DM	15.5	46.6	2.03	89.4	30	33.3	5,800	30	N	N
314	Neelamma	17442	60	F	Y	N	N	Loose stool	14.4	44.4	2.2	88.8	29	32.4	10,600	40	N	N
315	Mallappa	16989	81	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	5.5	19.7	0.58	84.5	24	27.9	4,900	110	Y	Dimorphic
316	Bhimashankar	17557	70	M	N	Y	N	Fever	11.8	34.5	2.69	88.2	29	30.6	6,900	15	Y	NCNC
317	Sidappa	17588	75	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	7.6	20.5	1	96.7	35	37.1	5,700	40	Y	NCNC
318	Ramesh	17475	65	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	7.1	20.6	1.41	88	30	35.4	13,700	45	Y	NCNC
319	Imamsab	17553	65	M	N	Y	N	COPD	10.7	34.6	6.05	89.9	28	30.9	23,100	10	Y	NCNC
320	Sonabai	59301	65	F	N	Y	N	Stroke	12	36	1.74	85.5	28	33.1	10,400	40	N	N

321	Subhas	16634	65	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	11.6	34	2.18	96	33	34.1	15,300	50	Y	NCNC
322	Dundappa	17760	76	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	12.1	37.2	1.92	89.6	29	36.2	7,000	40	Y	NCNC
323	Sateppa	204163	70	M	N	Y	N	Mass per vagina	9	28.2	1.84	61.8	20	31.9	18,300	55	Y	MCHC
324	Anandappa	17316	67	M	Y	Y	N	Giddiness	9.5	30.1	1.46	76.2	24	31.6	16,700	40	Y	NCHC
325	Jilam	205753	68	M	N	Y	N	DM	14	39.9	2.26	80	28	35.1	7,400	50	N	N
326	Sarojini	17739	60	F	Y	N	N	Breathlessness	12.5	36.9	3.39	78.7	27	33.9	9,600	35	N	N
327	Gangamma	17738	65	F	N	N	N	Fever	12.9	41	3.63	73.9	23	31.5	7,900	55	N	N
328	Jinappa	17428	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	7.8	25.7	3.52	64.1	20	30.4	7,200	55	Y	MCHC
329	Janakibai	204972	72	F	N	Y	N	Dermatitis	11.2	34.6	2.34	88.5	29	32.4	9,000	25	Y	NCNC
330	Rudragouda	281489	72	M	N	N	N	Cough	15.1	44.8	1.97	94.1	32	33.9	5,600	5	N	N
331	Sangappa	281599	70	M	Y	N	N	Cough	15.5	46.8	2.07	92.3	31	33.1	7,600	20	N	N
332	Suneeta	24387	60	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	11.3	32.4	2.48	82	29	34.9	11,700	25	Y	NCNC
333	Jaganath	24305	75	M	Y	N	N	Breathlessness	10.7	33.2	1.5	84.9	27	32.2	20,700	55	Y	NCNC
334	Hiraben	268933	80	F	N	N	N	Cough	12.1	34.6	4.47	86.1	31	35.2	7,600	20	N	N
335	Rudragouda	244241	75	M	N	N	N	Giddiness	14.2	42.8	1.71	93.7	32	33.8	6,400	40	N	N
336	Laxmibai	24195	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	7.2	19.1	2.37	91.4	34	37.1	10,900	100	Y	NCNC
337	Channamma	24454	72	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	10	31.7	3.68	83.5	26	31.5	10,600	45	Y	NCNC
338	Ramagond	24442	70	M	Y	Y	N	# Rt humerus	11.2	33.9	1.8	91.9	30	33	7,600	95	Y	NCNC
339	Malakappa	51139	65	M	Y	Y	N	Swelling on left hand	11.7	37.8	1.44	71.6	22	31	5,500	5	Y	NCHC
340	Shankar	51079	60	M	N	N	N	DM	14.5	44.2	3.9	78.8	25	32.8	12,500	15	N	N
341	Sheetadevi	51441	75	F	N	Y	N	Cellulitis	10.7	31.4	3.25	83.8	28	33	7,900	75	Y	NCNC
342	Shovanna	50985	78	F	N	N	N	Fever	13.4	40.4	2.75	98.5	33	33.2	8,500	10	N	N
343	Kinchappa	4325	65	M	Y	N	N	Back pain	11.9	35.2	3.23	81.9	26	29.9	6,800	40	Y	NCNC
344	Gumaste	50933	78	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	14.9	43.4	1.5	86.5	30	32.2	7,800	45	N	N
345	Shankreppa	4314	85	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	8.4	27.9	2.05	106	32	30.1	7,600	60	Y	Macrocytic
346	Gangabai	4301	60	F	N	Y	N	Malaria	10	33.2	3.13	67.1	20	30.1	7,600	85	Y	MCHC
347	Rangappa	4307	70	M	Y	N	N	Fever	13.2	38.8	1.66	90.2	31	34	7,500	10	N	N
348	Nabisab	4333	64	M	N	N	N	Breathlessness	13.6	39.8	2.23	84.1	29	34.2	8,800	5	N	N
349	Basamma	4339	70	F	N	N	N	Breathlessness	12.3	36.5	2.34	102	34	33.7	15,200	10	N	N
350	Siddramappa	4493	75	M	Y	Y	N	IHD	11.3	36.4	1.6	83.7	27	32.1	6,600	45	Y	NCNC

351	Mallappa	4504	63	M	N	N	N	Intestinal obstruction	13.5	41	3.19	89.5	30	32.9	8,500	5	N	N
352	Madanna	4539	64	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	10.9	35.9	2.18	83.1	25	30.4	5,500	70	Y	NCNC
353	V.R.Kustagi	53481	65	M	N	N	N	DM	13.6	43	2.08	89.8	28	31.6	7,500	5	N	N
354	Imamsab	4575	74	M	N	Y	N	Anemia	12.6	37.8	1.67	86.1	29	33.3	16,900	20	Y	NCNC
355	Basagond	24058	75	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10.5	33.6	2.59	83	26	31.3	6,200	10	Y	NCNC
356	Ramesh	278133	62	M	N	N	N	Weakness	13.9	41.2	3.64	104	35	33.7	12,100	10	N	N
357	Ishwar	277482	60	M	Y	N	N	Fever	14	40.5	2.68	85.2	30	36.5	7,700	5	N	N
358	Madiyappa	24018	60	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	8.3	26.2	1.37	92.3	29	31.7	8,900	30	Y	NCNC
359	Basumia	277428	60	F	N	Y	N	DM	8.4	27.2	1.69	72	22	30.9	9,600	60	Y	MCHC
360	Basappa	24077	65	M	N	N	N	Fever	9.9	31.2	3	89.4	28	31.7	8,000	50	Y	NCNC
361	Sadappagouda	23381	60	M	Y	Y	N	Chest pain	9.8	30.1	2.81	95.3	31	32.6	6,600	25	Y	NCNC
362	Jaganath	23990	75	M	N	Y	N	# humerus	10.5	35.5	8.42	68.7	20	29.3	19,200	85	Y	MCHC
363	Hullaya	24055	75	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	12.8	40.3	2.61	87.6	28	31.8	7,000	25	Y	NCNC
364	Godubai	24083	70	F	N	Y	N	Swelling in lower limb	8.7	26.3	1.7	82.3	28	32.6	9,600	40	Y	Dimorphic
365	Madevappa	276274	60	M	Y	Y	N	LVF	12.3	36.5	2.63	74.5	28	32.8	6,800	10	Y	NCNC
366	Bhidu	23920	68	M	N	Y	N	Weakness	5.4	17.6	0.48	80	25	30.7	5,800	110	Y	Dimorphic
367	Sangamma	3E+06	65	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	12.4	40.3	2.7	73.8	23	30.8	6,800	20	Y	NCHC
368	M.G.PaTil	275972	64	M	N	N	N	Tingling, numbness	17	48.2	3.62	94.2	34	38.2	16,200	5	N	N
369	Niganagouda	23908	65	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	11.1	32.1	2.34	81.7	28	34.6	8,800	100	Y	NCNC
370	Annamma	23909	60	F	N	Y	N	Pain in Rt Shoulder	12.2	39.7	3.65	81.9	25	30.7	20,000	50	N	N
371	Nimbawwa	23894	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.5	31.7	1.8	76.3	31	34.9	8,900	50	Y	NCNC
372	Devappa	23913	77	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	10	30.8	2.54	80.4	27	32.9	13,700	60	Y	NCNC
373	Balappa	23943	65	M	Y	Y	N	Cellulitis	10.1	31.3	2.54	97.2	31	32.3	8,500	45	Y	NCNC
374	Ramappa	23935	65	M	N	Y	N	DM, IHD	14.7	43.9	3.07	95.6	32	33.5	6,400	10	N	N
375	Yenkappa	23980	65	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	13.1	40.3	2	76.2	25	32.5	6,400	80	N	N
376	Samantappa	23973	75	M	N	Y	N	Gastroenteritis	11.5	35.7	2.05	74.7	24	32.2	13,000	30	Y	NCHC
377	Ratnabai	23959	75	F	N	Y	N	Hematemesis	10.3	32.3	1.2	72.4	24	31.9	8,000	60	Y	MCHC
378	Jadhav	23997	65	M	Y	N	N	Chest pain	8.1	29.4	1	68.9	19	27.6	23,300	10	Y	MCHC
379	Bagubai	23884	65	F	Y	Y	N	IHD	11.4	34.8	3.36	85.7	28	32.6	10,300	40	Y	NCNC

380	Madev	23445	60	M	N	N	N	Cough	15.4	45.9	2.22	82.7	28	33.5	18,200	10	N	N
381	Bhimashi	20585	80	M	N	Y	N	Intestinal obstruction	11.2	36	2.8	78.5	28	34.9	7,100	25	Y	NCNC
382	Nagappa	23420	70	M	Y	Y	N	Pain in Rt Shoulder	9.7	31.4	3.71	77.3	24	30.9	18,900	40	Y	NCHC
383	B.G.Mulimani	270774	63	M	N	Y	N	Diabetic foot	11.7	35.1	3.6	79.6	27	32.5	12,200	80	Y	NCNC
384	Barha	270586	78	M	N	N	N	Weakness	13.1	40.4	1.88	84.3	27	32.4	9,000	50	N	N
385	Porwal	77446	70	F	N	Y	N	Mets	12.3	35.7	2.9	83.2	29	34.5	6,400	40	N	N
386	Subadra	23442	61	F	N	Y	N	Abscess	12.6	38.8	4.65	87.6	28	32.5	19,100	60	N	N
387	Motilal	23450	70	M	Y	Y	N	Fistula	13.2	42.7	3.18	71.5	22	30.9	12,000	5	N	N
388	Mudansab	23493	65	M	N	N	N	DM	8.7	30.1	0.93	72.5	21	28.9	13,300	35	Y	MCHC
389	Monebai	23407	65	F	N	N	N	Fever	13.3	41.2	1.5	89.6	29	32.3	6,400	10	N	N
390	Sidappa	23660	65	M	N	N	N	Cough	12	31.1	2.11	88.6	34	38.2	5,500	50	Y	NCNC
391	Madnu	23636	85	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10.3	33	2.91	79.3	25	31.2	9,300	70	Y	NCHC
392	Vithal	272617	69	M	N	Y	N	Fever	16.8	48.5	1.37	86.9	30	34.6	18,100	10	N	N
393	Kantilal	271948	60	M	N	Y	N	DM	12.1	36.5	3.65	86.2	30	36.5	7,900	5	Y	NCNC
394	Sarojini	271746	65	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.4	33.5	2.19	106	36	34.2	6,000	60	Y	Macrocytic
395	Parvati	271718	63	F	N	Y	N	Fever	9.4	29.3	1.8	64.3	21	31.2	13,000	40	Y	MCHC
396	Hanabai	272619	60	F	N	Y	N	Dermatitis	8.6	29.2	3.83	98.7	20	29.5	8,800	40	Y	MCHC
397	Maruti	22431	60	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10	32.7	3.46	89.6	27	30.6	9,000	55	Y	NCNC
398	Ishwar	271713	70	M	N	N	N	Chest pain	13.5	38.3	1.48	96.2	34	35.2	6,200	5	N	N
399	Revamma	23612	65	F	N	Y	N	Atrophic rhinitis	13.8	45.4	3.64	75.8	26	32.1	8,100	10	N	N
400	Rukmani	23526	60	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	9	36.3	0.62	77.2	30	34	8,900	60	Y	NCNC
401	SK Giri	23656	61	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.2	33.5	1.5	77	26	33.4	21,700	90	Y	NCNC
402	Waly	23567	70	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	12.2	37.6	1.15	89.1	29	32.4	9,500	75	Y	NCNC
403	Bhumawwa	23599	65	F	Y	Y	N	Weakness	8.8	30.1	0.45	104	31	30.2	8,600	5	Y	Macrocytic
404	Boramma	23640	60	F	N	N	N	Fever	13.6	40.7	0.9	83.4	28	33.4	2,700	5	N	N
405	Gangawwa	24368	65	F	N	Y	N	HTN	10.4	31.5	2.34	82.5	27	33	15,300	45	Y	NCNC
406	Shantabai	25105	72	F	N	Y	N	Cough	11.9	34.4	2.96	84.3	29	34.6	8,400	50	Y	NCNC
407	Ayyappa	25237	65	M	Y	Y	N	Liver Cirrhosis	11.8	34.6	1.5	86.5	30	31.1	7,600	35	Y	NCNC
408	Yoga	3E+06	63	M	N	N	N	Swelling in lower limb	16	44	2.12	83.5	30	35.5	7,700	5	N	N

409	Chandrawwa	25254	65	M	N	Y	N	Cough	11.6	35.2	3.21	80.2	26	32.5	7,600	45	Y	NCNC
410	Bhima	25178	65	M	Y	N	N	Breathlessness	14.6	41.6	2.4	103.5	36	35.1	20,300	50	N	N
411	Srinivas	25247	64	M	N	N	N	Asthma	15.9	47.7	0.74	98.4	33	33.3	4,600	60	N	N
412	Janabai	25175	61	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	10.2	27.6	3.54	82.1	30	37	12,000	80	Y	NCNC
413	Balasab	25243	64	M	Y	Y	N	HTN	12.2	38.4	2.36	88.1	29	32.6	10,600	40	Y	NCNC
414	Varb	23820	75	M	N	Y	N	HTN	8.9	27.1	1.23	94.8	31	32.8	8,000	45	Y	NCNC
415	Laxmibai	23786	60	F	N	Y	N	Convulsion	11.8	34.4	2	80	29	34.3	9,000	30	Y	NCNC
416	Basappa	23719	78	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	14.9	43.9	2.36	82.6	29	35.9	6,800	10	N	N
417	Bangerawwa	23787	60	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	11.8	40.5	2.54	81	24	29.1	11,800	45	Y	NCHC
418	Shivappa	23796	68	M	Y	N	N	Swelling in lower limb	13.8	41.7	2.06	87.6	29	32.6	10,000	20	N	N
419	Nijamma	23870	70	F	N	Y	N	HTN	8.5	26.3	1.98	88.3	29	32.3	6,700	50	Y	NCNC
420	Gorawwa	23867	60	F	N	Y	N	#	7.7	24	1.91	114	37	32.1	3,800	20	Y	Macrocytic
421	Yamanappa	23864	65	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	12.2	38.9	2.42	82.2	26	31.4	15,700	15	Y	NCNC
422	Bagubai	23884	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.7	36.6	3.25	86.9	28	32	9,400	25	Y	NCNC
423	Laxmibai	23387	70	F	N	Y	N	Fall from height	9.5	35.2	3.16	81.5	22	27	9,600	55	Y	Dimorphic
424	Somappa	267978	60	M	Y	N	N	Breathlessness	13.9	41.8	2.65	90	33	34.6	7,500	50	N	N
425	Sharanabai	23303	63	F	N	N	N	Malaria	14.9	43.4	2.28	83.8	29	32.6	11,400	60	N	N
426	Sushilabai	23238	60	F	N	N	N	Fever	12	35.5	0.9	89.6	30	33.8	6,200	30	N	N
427	Shankargouda	267640	65	M	N	Y	N	Abscess	13.4	39.9	1.42	93.9	30	33.2	4,700	30	N	N
428	Latabai	267628	85	M	N	N	N	Weakness	13.7	41.3	1.61	85	28	33.2	12,100	5	N	N
429	Chandrasab	22501	75	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	10	31.3	2.26	80.3	26	31.9	7,300	60	Y	NCNC
430	Shivabai	23287	65	F	N	Y	N	UTI	11	33.2	2.12	82.8	27	33.1	9,600	75	Y	NCNC
431	Shantappa	22713	68	M	N	Y	N	TB	11.2	37.2	0.74	75.8	23	30.1	27,900	30	Y	NCHC
432	Gourawwa	3224	60	F	N	Y	N	Altered sensorium	11.4	34.3	2.65	91.7	30	32.4	7,200	45	Y	NCNC
433	Leela	3254	70	M	Y	N	N	DM	18.8	58.6	1.23	90.8	30	32.5	13,900	10	N	N
434	Mayya	3218	85	M	Y	Y	N	Cholera	11	34.4	2.36	88.9	28	32	6,800	40	Y	NCNC
435	Shantabai	37698	65	F	N	Y	N	IHD	10.7	33	2.32	95.9	31	32.4	8,400	35	Y	NCNC
436	Govindappa	34721	78	M	Y	Y	N	Gangrene	11.5	36.8	1.69	95.3	30	32.1	8,100	20	Y	NCNC
437	Makawwa	2681	60	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.2	33.5	2.76	84.5	29	33	17,800	55	Y	NCNC
438	Chandappa	37601	70	M	N	N	N	COPD	15.5	45.7	2.04	92.2	31	33.6	8,500	20	N	N

439	Laxmibai	37384	73	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	11.4	33.7	3.14	84.5	29	33.8	6,100	25	Y	NCNC
440	Ramanna	36471	87	M	Y	N	N	Swelling in lower limb	10.6	33.9	2.22	89.4	28	31.3	4,300	50	Y	NCNC
441	Ningamma	3209	75	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	10.7	34.1	4.52	84	26	31.4	8,400	35	Y	NCNC
442	Borawwa	10868	60	F	N	N	N	Ulcer	10.5	32	1.05	87.7	29	32.8	5,400	70	Y	NCNC
443	Nathubai	35661	65	F	Y	N	N	CVA	11.5	35.7	3.01	83.8	27	32.2	5,900	40	Y	NCNC
444	Babgappagouda	4405	65	M	Y	N	N	Weakness	12.2	38.1	1.5	122	39	32	16,200	40	Y	Macrocytic
445	Tulsa	51585	73	F	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	23.1	69.2	0.58	80.8	28	35.2	2,800	40	N	N
446	Sivappa	3849	80	F	N	Y	N	Back pain	8.8	26.2	2.3	101	34	33.6	8,800	20	Y	Macrocytic
447	Sangawwa	3231	65	F	N	Y	N	Cough	10.3	32.9	2.14	82.1	26	32.5	5,400	65	Y	NCNC
448	Gangabai	4139	70	F	N	N	N	# femur	12.6	41.9	3	83.3	25	30	12,700	25	N	N
449	Sidnagouda	4149	79	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	11	35.5	3.91	67.9	21	31	15,700	40	Y	MCHC
450	Allisab	4188	80	M	N	N	N	Weakness	12.9	38.8	1.85	83.6	29	33.2	8,500	10	Y	NCNC
451	Tukawwa	4195	65	F	N	Y	N	Hematuria	10.8	36.2	3.14	85	25	29.8	11,000	90	Y	NCNC
452	Bhimaraya	3448	90	M	N	Y	N	Fever	10.8	33.6	2.36	98.8	32	32.1	6,600	55	Y	NCNC
453	Goura	49193	60	F	N	Y	N	Urinary retention	11.1	34.2	3.86	81.8	27	32.5	19,300	50	Y	NCNC
454	Badalabai	49000	60	F	N	N	N	Fever with chills	11.7	33.9	2.58	99.1	33	34.5	5,300	25	Y	NCNC
455	Gurappa	4185	60	M	Y	Y	N	Hematuria	13.3	39.4	3.23	91.8	31	33.8	8,500	50	N	N
456	Yamanawwa	3792	65	F	N	N	N	Fever	10.2	33	2.97	82.3	25	30.9	7,300	55	Y	NCNC
457	Muawwa	4177	60	F	N	Y	N	Hematemesis	13.2	42	2.46	88.6	28	31.4	8,200	25	N	N
458	Potamosappa	4191	75	M	Y	N	N	Fever	13.7	41.9	1.5	95.2	31	32.7	7,300	45	N	N
459	Neelamma	87514	75	F	N	N	N	TB	12	37.2	1.97	82.5	27	32.3	16,400	75	N	N
460	Yalappa	7182	65	M	N	Y	N	DM	11.4	34.2	3.73	87.4	29	33.3	21,800	90	Y	NCNC
460	Sahibgouda	7188	62	M	Y	Y	N	Loose stool	2.8	8.2	2.44	98.8	34	34.1	7,800	35	Y	Dimorphic
461	Shantabai	87008	67	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	8.5	28	1.15	75.1	23	30.4	4,000	55	Y	MCHC
462	Madrawwa	7162	75	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	12.5	38.8	1.68	91.6	29	33.5	5,800	70	Y	NCNC
463	Seetabai	7161	70	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	7.2	25.3	3.87	80.9	31	38.5	39,600	85	Y	Dimorphic
464	Mudgappa	7192	77	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	8.6	28.9	1.63	78.5	32	34.8	7,400	40	Y	NCNC
465	Chanamma	7157	60	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	11.8	38	4.18	91	28	31.1	8,600	35	Y	NCNC
467	Ram	6202	84	M	N	Y	N	Gluteal abscess	4.9	16.1	1.96	81.6	31	28.7	15,100	55	Y	Dimorphic
468	Kulkar	6224	89	M	Y	N	N	Cough	15.9	46.2	2.95	88	30	34.4	12,400	5	N	N

469	Raju	6136	62	M	N	Y	N	Chest pain	12.2	37.5	1.93	102	33	32.5	13,500	25	Y	Macrocytic
470	Ratnabai	5620	72	F	Y	Y	N	Fever	11.3	36.4	2.62	84.2	29	32.6	27,400	70	Y	NCNC
471	Bagawwa	6205	60	F	N	N	N	Prolapse	11.8	40.5	1.5	87.9	26	29.1	5,500	5	Y	NCNC
472	Yalewwa	6322	65	F	N	N	N	Fever	12.9	39.2	1.88	92	30	32.9	6,700	30	N	N
473	Hanamantraj	6441	70	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	10	31	1.35	88.6	29	32.3	12,500	25	Y	NCNC
474	Sahebgouda	6670	71	M	N	Y	N	Altered sensorium	11.8	37.9	1.9	85.7	26	31.1	9,900	25	Y	NCNC
475	Hanamanth	6502	60	M	N	Y	N	Fever with chills	10.7	33.5	2.5	96.3	31	31.9	13,000	50	Y	NCNC
476	Gurubai	5932	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.8	33.1	1.87	80	26	32.6	10,700	100	Y	NCNC
477	Prakash	6512	65	M	Y	Y	N	Inf.wall MI	11.8	35.5	2.48	79.4	30	33.2	10,700	90	Y	NCNC
478	Shantamma	6468	65	F	N	Y	N	Pneumonia	10.6	32.6	2.11	95.3	31	32.5	6,500	60	Y	NCNC
479	Durgappa	78088	60	M	N	Y	N	Eczema	11.1	35.4	2.69	76.3	23	29.6	9,700	55	Y	NCHC
480	Shankrawwa	6985	60	F	N	Y	N	Fever, cough	11.9	34.4	2.11	93.2	32	34.6	6,300	45	Y	NCNC
481	Manawwa	78385	70	F	N	Y	N	Convulsion	12.4	38.3	2.7	82.7	26	31.6	12,400	5	N	N
482	Gurajswamy	6481	65	M	Y	N	N	Fracture	14.7	47	2.55	98.5	31	31.3	23,300	15	N	N
483	Setawwa	7025	60	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.3	35.3	2.06	80.2	26	32	7,900	55	Y	NCNC
484	Shantappa	5408	60	M	Y	Y	N	Bronchitis	10.4	31.5	2.09	64	21	32.9	3,400	35	Y	MCHC
485	yalawwa	6746	65	F	N	Y	N	Cough	10.1	30.8	1.68	88.5	29	32.8	4,700	60	Y	NCNC
486	Renabai	6864	81	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	5.2	14.9	1.5	113	40	34.9	3,900	65	Y	Dimorphic
487	Menabai	7023	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	8.1	25.9	0.8	67.4	21	31.3	6,400	60	Y	MCHC
488	Mallikarjun	7052	60	M	N	Y	N	Gastritis	10	30.9	2.38	82	27	32.4	13,600	100	Y	NCNC
489	Amaraya	85487	68	F	N	Y	N	Bronchitis	12.7	35.4	2.45	105	38	25.9	10,500	30	N	N
490	Sidramappa	7014	75	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	9.6	28.1	1.86	109.3	37	34.2	4,500	30	Y	Macrocytic
491	YK Supur	84691	60	M	N	Y	N	Swelling of neck	9.9	29.4	2.39	84	28	33.7	6,800	70	Y	NCNC
492	Mahantesh	7008	60	M	Y	Y	N	DM	11.4	34.8	2.05	84.1	28	32.8	16,100	25	Y	NCNC
493	Nurabai	2268	60	F	N	Y	N	TB	8.4	26.2	0.74	80.4	26	32.1	1,800	90	Y	NCHC
494	Yallappa	7006	70	M	Y	N	N	Swelling of neck	13.1	43.4	2.86	95.8	29	30.2	21,900	5	N	N
495	Chappar	3234	70	F	N	Y	N	Cough	9.5	30.7	5.54	84.3	26	30.9	9,600	60	Y	NCNC
496	Lenkappa	3260	60	M	N	N	N	Dermatitis	15.7	42.5	1.9	79.9	30	36.9	11,100	20	N	N
497	Neelamma	3202	82	F	N	N	N	Pneumonia	12.4	37.9	1.35	84.8	28	32.7	14,300	50	N	N
498	Manawwa	3124	69	F	N	Y	N	DM	7.1	21.9	1.5	131	43	32.4	4,100	100	Y	Macrocytic
499	Vithal	6821	78	M	N	Y	N	Urinary retention	14.9	43.2	2.71	86.2	31	32.6	12,200	30	N	N

500	Mahamudsab	6862	80	M	N	N	N	HTN	13.2	39.1	2.28	92.4	31	33	8,800	10	N	N
501	Sitabai	6153	70	F	N	Y	N	Haemorrhoid	12.3	39.8	4.71	86	27	30.9	15,700	25	N	N
502	Syanappa	6673	60	M	N	Y	N	Liver trauma	6.7	20.6	3.18	89.2	29	32.5	9,300	55	Y	NCNC
503	Shantabai	82720	70	F	N	N	N	Cerebral malaria	12.5	38	3.25	93.6	31	32.4	7,500	75	N	N
504	Parvati	82259	60	F	N	N	N	Burn	12.7	36	3.25	76.5	36	34.2	7,100	20	N	N
505	Tipanna	6814	60	M	Y	N	N	Prolapse	13.1	39.3	2.11	89	30	33.5	7,800	35	N	N
506	Balappa	6820	60	M	N	Y	N	Chest pain	12.6	40.7	1.5	82.6	26	31	8,200	5	Y	NCNC
507	Bagbai	6832	85	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.3	35.7	2.43	82	26	30.2	8,400	35	Y	NCNC
508	Golamma	82274	65	F	N	Y	N	Abscess	13.6	39.4	2.76	88.5	31	34.5	6,600	35	N	N
509	Jalaj	82807	68	M	N	Y	N	Joint pain	11.2	33.2	2.7	73.2	25	33.2	9,400	25	Y	NCHC
510	Salimsab	6846	65	M	N	Y	N	Cough	11.6	34.4	1.5	74.9	25	33.7	8,200	45	Y	NCNC
511	Ganga	83420	60	M	N	N	N	UTI	12.2	37.5	2.21	78.6	26	32.5	7,500	75	Y	NCNC
512	Babusab	6810	60	M	N	N	N	Gluteal abscess	13.4	41.4	3.04	87	28	31.5	9,000	20	N	N
513	Ramesh	6827	65	M	Y	Y	N	Lower limb#	10.5	32.1	1.92	81.2	27	32.7	18,800	80	Y	NCNC
514	Sidappa	6786	62	M	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	14.2	45.8	3.16	83.9	27	31.7	13,200	25	N	N
515	Yamanappa	3804	75	M	Y	N	N	Fever & cough	13.2	39.2	1.93	101	33	33.1	18,600	40	N	N
516	Shaiyawwa	3787	70	F	N	Y	N	Fever	7.2	20.9	2.65	86	30	34.4	12,000	95	Y	NCNC
517	Yallawa	3812	70	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	11.6	37.2	3.44	90.5	28	31.2	10,100	50	Y	NCNC
518	Nadivalamma	3799	71	F	N	Y	N	IHD, DM	8.9	29.7	3.18	101	30	30	9,100	60	Y	Macrocytic
519	Tismawwa	2927	80	F	N	Y	N	Rheumatoid arthritis	8.1	26.9	4.76	80.5	24	30.1	4,300	85	Y	Dimorphic
520	Gautamrao	3760	70	M	N	Y	N	Abscess	12.7	42	2.4	90.7	27	30.2	10,700	30	Y	NCNC
521	Sidramappa	44327	60	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	12.1	37.9	3.73	85.6	28	31.9	7,100	50	Y	NCNC
522	Zulekha	3415	66	F	N	Y	N	Unconsciousness	11	34.4	2.09	88.2	28	32	7,700	55	Y	NCNC
523	G.S.Kumbar	3739	66	M	Y	Y	N	Chest pain	12.8	40.2	2.15	73.8	24	31.8	8,300	15	Y	NCHC
524	Guru	3784	70	M	N	N	N	Fever	15.6	45.2	1.67	85.8	30	34.5	8,300	20	N	N
525	Yalawwa	3586	65	F	N	Y	N	Cough	5.1	19.7	3.43	62.9	16	25.9	11,600	125	Y	MCHC
526	Viswanath	36981	79	M	Y	Y	N	Pain abdomen	14.7	44	2.36	95.3	29	32.8	8,300	10	N	N
527	Chabbi	44542	63	M	Y	N	N	Pain abdomen	15.2	43.2	1.53	90.2	32	35.2	4,400	5	N	N
528	Chawlabai	6086	60	M	N	N	N	Vomiting	11.9	38	2.6	86.2	31	35.2	13,600	50	Y	NCNC
529	Shrishail	3778	65	M	N	Y	N	Urticaria	12.5	37.3	1.5	101	33	34.6	16,800	45	Y	Macrocytic

530	Ramappa	6089	70	M	Y	N	N	Pain in Lt thigh	14	44.1	1.59	86	28	32.5	9,300	15	N	N
531	Bagawwa	6056	70	M	N	Y	N	Bullous pemphigoid	12.1	37.1	2.61	78.6	26	32.6	3,000	55	Y	NCNC
532	Vallikar	6673	72	M	Y	Y	N	Abdoman distension	11.1	33.6	1.9	80.2	26	33.5	5,500	25	Y	NCNC
533	Rajusab	6074	70	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	3.7	13	4.54	62	17	27.9	7,800	115	Y	MCHC
534	Sahadevi	6077	62	F	N	Y	N	Abscess	9.9	31.2	2.2	83	26	31.5	10,500	55	Y	NCHC
535	Mahadev	74298	65	M	N	Y	N	Tonsillitis	11.8	34.1	1.64	84.6	29	34.2	12,900	20	Y	NCNC
536	Gurupadappa	6207	60	M	Y	Y	N	Cough	7.6	25.4	2.57	68.1	20	29.9	5,800	40	Y	MCHC
537	Susalabai	6215	60	F	N	Y	N	Inguinal swelling	10.5	35.6	1.61	84.2	25	29.3	6,100	15	Y	NCHC
538	Shiva	6190	60	M	N	N	N	RA	14	43.6	2.34	92.6	30	32.1	14,000	20	N	N
539	Ravi	74315	64	M	N	Y	N	Myalgia	5.5	17.1	3.37	78.2	26	32.9	12,800	70	Y	NCNC
540	Bagavant	4432	70	M	N	Y	N	Acute GE	12.8	37.9	3.89	94	32	33.8	10,500	20	Y	NCNC
541	Peera	5897	60	M	N	Y	N	HTN	13.8	39.8	1.8	82.1	29	34.7	5,700	20	N	N
542	Seetabai	5765	80	F	N	Y	N	Dermatitis	5.2	17	5.29	70	21	30.6	16,100	120	Y	MCHC
543	Yamunabai	5832	68	F	N	Y	N	Cough	12.7	40	2.61	85.3	27	31.8	13,000	65	N	N
544	Malwappa	5874	79	M	N	Y	N	Fever	10.2	31.3	1.5	84.8	28	32.6	9,100	55	Y	NCNC
545	Malappa	5879	79	M	N	N	N	Bleeding PV	13.2	41	1.81	101	33	32.2	11,700	60	N	N
546	Anandappa	5836	65	M	Y	Y	N	Prolapse	9.4	29	2.12	80	25	32.4	8,300	25	Y	NCNC
547	Dodoveni	3875	60	M	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.6	35.1	0.45	80	26	33.6	8,000	95	Y	NCNC
548	Shantappa	5822	70	F	N	Y	N	Bronchitis	10.6	32	0.66	87	29	32.9	13,400	40	Y	NCNC
549	Davappa	5876	80	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	12.5	39.4	1.5	92.9	30	31.7	10,600	60	Y	NCNC
550	Argun	5861	62	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	13.2	32.5	1.5	85	33	34.2	10,500	25	N	N
551	Boramamma	170407	65	F	N	N	N	Fever	12.3	37	1.68	90.5	30	33.2	8,200	20	N	N
552	Bhimappa	5865	70	M	Y	Y	N	Altered sensorium	11.6	37.4	3.72	80.4	25	31	12,400	40	Y	NCHC
553	Basanna	5849	65	M	N	Y	N	Cough	12.5	37.8	2.09	83.6	27	33.2	17,600	60	Y	NCNC
554	Bangaigund	6476	62	M	Y	N	N	Fever	14.1	42	3.75	83	27	32.9	11,300	15	N	N
555	Kashibai	5877	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.2	32.5	2.63	81	26	31.2	9,200	25	Y	NCNC
556	Gurappa	6491	69	M	N	Y	N	Vomiting	12.2	37.6	1.98	91.5	30	32.4	6,000	30	Y	NCNC
557	Basvant	6442	65	M	Y	Y	N	Hernia	6.4	19	1	89.2	30	33.7	15,700	10	Y	Dimorphic
558	Biradar	6061	81	M	Y	Y	N	Prolapse	11.1	32.1	3.1	92	31	34.6	7,800	75	Y	NCNC

559	Saradu	6036	60	F	N	N	N	Cough	14.4	45.3	2.14	77.6	25	31.8	14,500	25	N	N
560	Pahamanteya	6043	60	M	Y	Y	N	Breathlessness	12.2	38	1.56	84.4	27	32.1	4,000	35	Y	NCNC
561	Ratnawwa	6056	70	F	N	Y	N	Swelling	11.6	36.4	2.79	76.3	24	31.9	5,500	20	Y	NCHC
562	Hanamantaya	6043	68	M	N	Y	N	Fever	12.5	38	1.61	82.5	27	32.8	5,000	55	Y	NCNC
563	Rajesh	6038	65	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	11.2	37.4	2.73	81	24	29.3	10,700	40	Y	NCHC
564	Latabai	73086	60	F	N	Y	N	Vomiting	7.2	25	4.14	69.1	20	28.8	15,900	120	Y	MCHC
565	Rajubai	72809	80	F	N	Y	N	Ca Lung	7	23	69.3	21.1	31	30.4	10,300	20	Y	MCHC
566	Laxmibai	6051	64	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11.8	37	1.65	94.4	30	31.7	7,300	40	Y	NCNC
567	Balappa	5784	65	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	9.7	29.3	5.45	91	29	32.6	13,000	55	Y	NCNC
568	Gattu	6062	65	M	N	Y	N	Inguinal swelling	13.1	39.9	1.88	80	26	32.8	10,100	25	N	N
569	Kallappa	6080	60	M	Y	Y	N	# neck of femur	13.6	42	2.36	85.7	31	32.9	8,800	15	N	N
570	Jitappa	6679	79	M	N	Y	N	Cough	10.7	33	3.85	83	27	32.4	15,000	95	Y	NCNC
571	Ramesh	6729	80	M	N	Y	N	Fever	11.7	35.7	1.2	93.2	31	32.8	3,000	40	Y	NCNC
572	Yallappa	5194	60	M	Y	Y	N	Lipoma	11	34.5	1.5	88.9	29	31.9	12,400	85	Y	NCNC
573	Sidanagouda	6202	84	M	Y	N	N	Fever	8.9	27	1.51	82.9	27	32.8	13,500	95	Y	NCNC
574	Sanappa	6690	65	M	N	Y	N	AR +MR	11.9	42.9	0.64	80	22	27.6	8,600	35	Y	NCHC
575	Syanappa	6673	60	M	Y	Y	N	Swelling lower limb	4.6	14	4.54	83.8	28	32.9	10,300	10	Y	Dimorphic
576	Sangmesh	6678	60	M	N	Y	N	DM	8.7	29.1	4	69	21	29.6	14,200	25	Y	MCHC
577	Biradar	81047	65	M	N	Y	N	Psoriatic arthritis	13.6	39.2	2.61	92.7	32	34.7	15,700	80	N	N
578	Shivanna	7203	65	M	N	Y	N	Swelling over Rt arm	10.3	32.8	3.12	96.3	30	31.5	8,800	50	Y	NCNC
579	Siddamma	6699	80	F	N	Y	N	Fever	7.1	21.1	1.5	85.8	28	33.6	10,100	30	Y	NCNC
580	Chavan	7163	62	F	N	N	N	Breathlessness	12.6	36.7	1.97	85	29	34.9	12,700	50	N	N
581	Hajilal	7171	64	M	Y	Y	N	Acute GE	13	39.7	3.14	87	28	32.6	10,600	25	N	N
582	Pearawwa	7210	75	F	N	Y	N	Anemia	12.4	38.1	3.36	82	26	31.2	17,400	25	N	N
583	Sobhabai	6002	65	F	N	Y	N	Vomiting	7.2	22.8	7.77	85.1	27	31.6	7,400	120	Y	NCNC
584	Rayabanna	7135	85	M	Y	Y	N	BPH	10.4	31.9	2.71	99.4	32	32.6	7,500	40	Y	Macrocytic
585	Basamma	7155	70	F	N	Y	N	Breathlessness	11.5	35.5	2.27	85	27	32.6	11,300	40	Y	NCNC
586	Shantabai	7104	70	F	N	Y	N	TB	11.9	36.3	2.1	86.4	28	32.6	6,000	35	Y	NCNC
587	Ramdu	6828	65	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	2.4	10.4	0.79	76.3	17	23.5	13,000	15	Y	Dimorphic

588	Nelpaksya	87340	70	M	N	Y	N	# Femur	10.8	35.8	3.11	73.2	22	30.2	8,200	75	Y	MCHC
589	Yamunappa	7076	78	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	6.7	24.8	3.15	70.7	19	27	4,100	100	Y	MCHC
590	Chandu	6828	65	M	N	Y	N	Weakness	2.1	8.9	0.6	69	16	23.6	16,100	120	Y	MCHC
591	Chipala	4481	74	M	Y	Y	N	Chest pain	12.6	38.1	3.13	99.7	32	36.2	14,100	5	Y	NCNC
592	Sharan	4200	62	M	N	Y	N	Cough	6.2	20.2	9.83	62.3	18	30.5	23,100	110	Y	MCHC
593	Shivappa	4474	75	M	Y	Y	N	Loose stool	3.7	13.2	3.24	67.7	19	28.3	6,200	65	Y	MCHC
594	Chimalgi	4469	71	F	N	Y	N	BPH	8.5	24.8	4.1	89.5	31	34.3	6,200	55	Y	NCNC
595	Samabai	4391	65	F	N	N	N	Fever	11.9	36.8	2.75	98	31	32.5	10,000	25	Y	NCNC
596	Santa	4432	70	M	N	Y	N	UTI	11.7	35.6	3.97	95.7	32	32.9	11,400	10	Y	NCNC
597	Neelamma	3202	80	F	N	Y	N	Stroke	8.5	24.9	1.33	83	28	34.1	4,700	75	Y	NCNC
598	Anusuya	51897	61	F	N	Y	N	Fever	10.9	35.3	2.98	86.3	26	30.9	12,400	75	Y	NCNC
599	Jaganath	4390	75	M	Y	Y	N	Urinary retention	7.7	28.7	5.26	56.7	15	26.8	13,200	10	Y	MCHC
600	Channamma	3792	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever with chills	9.2	38.2	2.65	79.3	26	31.2	16,700	80	Y	NCHC
601	Kallangouda	4456	60	M	Y	Y	N	Hematuria	13.1	46.1	1.2	84.1	24	28.4	3,400	5	N	N
602	Sivappa	4478	60	M	N	N	N	Fever	13	40.4	2.08	85.2	28	32.2	5,600	10	N	N
603	Shivraj	4445	62	M	Y	Y	N	Hematemesis	10.7	31.8	1.67	113	38	33.6	7,900	80	Y	Macrocytic
604	Gouda	4405	60	M	N	Y	N	Fever	12.6	37.2	2.36	117	39	32.7	11,200	65	Y	Macrocytic
605	Yamallappa	4468	75	M	Y	Y	N	TB	11.3	34.3	1.4	81.3	26	30.8	16,500	50	Y	NCNC
606	Hasman	4458	68	M	N	Y	N	DM	8.6	28.1	3.35	72.1	22	30.6	4,100	25	Y	MCHC
607	Sonabai	4340	66	F	N	Y	N	Loose stool	8.5	28.1	7.68	80.7	23	28.1	14,600	90	Y	NCHC
608	Ramappa	4424	68	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	1.8	7.9	1.6	70.5	16	22.8	1,600	25	Y	Dimorphic
609	Dewappa	4466	68	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	10.4	32.1	2.35	83.2	27	32.4	8,800	5	Y	NCNC
610	Yamanappa	4002	60	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	9.6	29	3.94	74.9	25	33.1	34,500	75	Y	NCHC
611	Shivanna	4068	85	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	10.4	32.9	5.42	85	27	31.6	12,200	25	Y	NCNC
612	Gangabai	4082	98	F	N	Y	N	Chest pain	9.9	31.3	1.09	96	31	31.6	13,700	20	Y	NCNC
613	Kashibai	4059	72	F	N	Y	N	Gluteal abscess	10.2	33.6	1.88	78.3	24	30.4	8,400	55	Y	NCHC
614	Sunanda	4018	80	F	N	Y	N	Cough	12.2	37.5	2.49	87	28	32.5	9,400	5	Y	NCNC
615	Ramchandra	4093	68	M	Y	Y	N	Chest pain	12.3	37.6	1.5	87.6	29	32.9	11,200	45	Y	NCNC
616	Gagan	4043	69	M	N	Y	N	Fever	7.9	25.5	4.5	94	29	31.6	7,600	95	Y	NCNC
617	Santabai	3987	70	F	N	Y	N	Prolapse	8.8	27.5	1.97	76	25	32.8	5,900	25	Y	NCHC

618	Sidram	4064	70	M	Y	Y	N	TB	13	38.2	2.46	94.4	32	33.5	6,000	15	N	N
619	Bhimabai	4054	60	F	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	10.7	33.6	2.01	89.3	29	31.6	4,300	65	Y	NCNC
620	Irawwa	3925	65	F	N	Y	N	Swelling in lower limb	10.6	33.4	2.89	73.4	24	31.7	8,300	20	Y	MCHC
621	Yallawwa	3920	60	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	9.5	30.1	1.93	93.8	29	31.6	7,400	25	Y	NCNC
622	Madon	2927	72	F	N	Y	N	Ulcer	8	26.4	4.19	77	23	30.3	8,400	25	Y	NCHC
623	Parnath	4657	60	F	N	Y	N	CVA	12.1	36.2	2.56	83.2	27	31.9	15,900	55	N	N
624	Mudgappa	4678	70	M	Y	Y	N	Weakness	13.4	42	1.55	81	26	31.2	1,300	25	N	N
625	Chanappa	4629	60	M	N	N	N	Pain abdomen	13.6	42.1	2.58	90	29	32.3	5,800	15	N	N
626	MR Pasat	57698	60	M	N	Y	N	Back pain	12.4	35.7	2.48	83	29	34.7	12,700	45	Y	NCNC
627	Chenamelappa	4671	70	M	N	Y	N	Cough	12.1	39.6	3.12	76	23	30.6	12,300	10	Y	NCHC
628	Peerappa	4871	60	M	Y	Y	N	# femur	9.7	29.4	2.1	89	29	33.6	8,100	5	Y	NCNC
629	MG Patil	57545	65	M	N	Y	N	Fever	16.3	47.7	2.96	93	31	34.6	6,200	5	N	N
630	Nngamma	58117	65	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	11.2	35.1	3.16	90	28	31.6	6,800	25	Y	NCNC
631	Sarubai	57599	65	F	N	Y	N	Hematuria	13.3	40.7	2.9	80.9	28	32.7	6,000	5	N	N
632	Anjewwa	2528	76	F	N	Y	N	Fever	13.4	41.2	1.86	92.2	30	32.6	13,300	40	N	N
633	Danamma	2484	79	F	N	Y	N	Weakness	9	28.8	3.27	89.7	28	31.3	10,900	80	Y	NCNC
634	Sonabai	2421	60	F	N	Y	N	Altered sensorium	8.6	25.6	5.12	86.5	29	33.6	18,400	65	Y	NCNC
635	Bandagisab	2980	69	M	N	N	N	Fever with chills	13.1	37.6	1.79	83.9	29	34.8	10,000	60	N	N
636	Somangouda	2494	65	M	Y	Y	N	Fever	9.5	26.3	0.6	106	39	36.1	4,200	50	Y	Macrocytic
637	Madiwalappa	2473	73	M	Y	Y	N	Inf.wall MI	4.4	12.5	0.56	113.6	40	35.2	5,900	105	Y	Dimorphic
638	Lachapa	1707	70	M	Y	Y	N	Pneumonia	9.5	31	2.39	102.3	31	30.6	4,200	70	Y	Macrocytic
639	Shaila	2508	60	F	N	N	N	Eczema	11.5	33.7	1.83	83.8	29	34.1	10,100	60	Y	NCNC
640	Y U Surplus	28845	60	M	Y	Y	N	Fever, cough	9.3	29	2.07	86.1	28	32.1	6,000	50	Y	NCNC
641	Borawwa	29445	67	M	N	Y	N	Convulsion	9.9	32.9	3.86	80.6	24	30.1	7,700	20	Y	NCHC
642	Channamma	2204	70	F	N	Y	N	Fracture	9.9	34.6	3.21	71.8	21	28.6	7,800	65	Y	MCHC
643	Kaloleppa	29054	60	M	N	N	N	Fever	13.8	41.9	2.09	85	29	32.9	8,200	10	N	N
644	Parvati	29149	75	M	N	Y	N	Bronchitis	11.6	36.6	1.98	79	25	31.9	7,300	5	Y	NCNC
645	Mahesh	2453	73	M	N	Y	N	Cough	4.7	13.4	0.8	113.6	40	35.1	5,300	115	Y	Dimorphic
646	Bhimasha	28847	75	M	N	Y	N	Pain abdomen	11.3	34.7	2.7	95.3	31	32.6	5,900	80	Y	NCNC
647	Shankamma	29243	65	F	N	Y	N	Fever	11	33.3	3.02	96.9	31	32.4	6,200	90	Y	NCNC

648	Sushila	29281	66	F	N	Y	N	Gastritis	13.1	39.9	2.31	91.3	30	32.8	8,000	10	N	N
649	Saidusab	2499	65	M	Y	Y	N	Bronchitis	12.3	37.6	3.07	93.3	31	32.7	8,000	30	Y	NCNC
650	Y M Biradar	29795	60	M	N	Y	N	Cough	13.5	41.1	2.77	84.2	27	32.8	12,900	20	N	N
651	Nagamma	29782	62	F	N	Y	N	Swelling of neck	12.7	36.9	1.7	80.4	28	34.4	8,200	45	N	N
652	Nagawwa	29822	70	F	N	Y	N	DM	9.6	30.7	3.17	86	27	31.2	6,200	40	Y	NCNC
653	Semawwa	2490	88	F	N	N	N	TB	14.1	45.3	1.56	93.8	23	31.3	11,300	5	N	N
654	Bhimabai	4054	60	F	N	Y	N	Swelling of neck	10.7	33.6	2.01	89.3	29	31.6	4,300	65	Y	NCNC